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BENEFITS THROUGH EARTH OBSERVATIONS

**Annex to the ECOPOTENTIAL second periodic report:
Survey on communication and dissemination activities**

(Annex to Periodic Technical Report –part B - 2nd reporting period)

Period Covered: 1st December 2016 – 31st May 2018

Period: Second Reporting Period

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1. Executive Summary

This report is an annex to the second periodic reporting of Work Package 12 of the H2020 R&I project ECOPOTENTIAL (Grant Agreement n. 641762). It is aimed to verify the implementation of the Communication and Dissemination plan (D12.4).

As like as for the first report, it contains:

1. The communication activities reported in Table 1 of the C&D plan (D12.4) and the status of their implementation
2. The indicators of communication and dissemination performance (Table 2 of the C&D plan)
3. The relevant statistics on the access to the ECOPOTENTIAL website
4. An outline of social media activities
5. The list of conferences and other dissemination events where ECOPOTENTIAL has been presented (either presentations of the project as a whole and scientific results presentations)
6. The list of all Open Access peer reviewed publications, highlighting the Open Access publications published within this reporting period.

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2. Communication Activities foreseen in the C&D plan – status of implementation

The status of implementation of the actions reported in “Table I: Summary of actions” of the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D12.4) has been checked, with reference to the second reporting period.

The following actions have been undertaken from Dec 2016 up to date:

- Project website: upgrading and maintenance with sections targeted at different audiences, including security and implementation of data protection policy; three new websites have been created by partners on specific themes:
 - o Protected Areas from Space (maps) – partner: CREA: <http://maps.ecopotential-project.eu/>
 - o ECOPOTENTIAL4Schools – partner: UNILE: <http://193.204.79.105/ecopotential/>
 - o Protecting Marine Mammals in Crowded Waters – partner: GRID-Arendal (UNEP): <https://grid-arendal.maps.arcgis.com/apps/Cascade/index.html?appid=54b862ef079445d9a99b8f6249249e4d>
- Quarterly newsletter: release of five new issues and implementation of data protection policy
- Social Media accounts maintenance and use (Facebook, Twitter)
- Science policy interface and experience sharing: list of event organised
- Visual tools: videos, posters created and shown at events and on the ECOPOTENTIAL website.
- Printed material (“SPACED” booklet, Italian, Spanish, French and German versions of the ECOPOTENTIAL leaflet, calendar) realised
- Project deliverables made available through the website
- Scientific Publications on Journals: 47 out of total 61 new papers on peer reviewed journals published, and 17 out of 18 new other peer reviewed publications (book chapters, peer reviewed proceedings), for a total of 79 publications since the beginning of the project.
- Presentations at conferences and workshops: 83 new presentation at conferences and 108 presentations at workshops given
- Science schools: 2 new science schools organised
- Internal communications (discussion board, email, teleconferences): maintenance of mailing lists, cloud communication platform, teleconference platform
- One Photo exhibition organised and displayed in Bruxelles at the European Parliament and at the Committee of the Regions
- Project’s workshops: three workshops organised (Helsinki, Washington, Bruxelles) plus two workshops devoted to Protected Areas staff (Pisa 2017 and Pisa 2018).
- Science-policy study carried out in WP11 with strong communication component
- Citizen Science actions: thematic workshops and exercises organised.

During the last year of the project, the establishment of the Public Discussion Forum, the ECOPOTENTIAL Virtual Laboratory Platform and the establishment of a Community of practise (CoP) will be completed.

The communication and dissemination activities undertaken during the first and second period and the sum for the two periods may be summarized as follows (the sum represents the data currently uploaded in the EU Participant Portal – System for Grant Management – Dissemination and Communication activities).

Table 1: Summary of communication and dissemination activities as reported in the EU reporting portal SyGMA

ACTIVITY	# 1° Rep period	# 2° Rep period	Total #
Organisation of a workshop	3	13	16
Press release	7	37	44
Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)	3	9	12
Exhibition		6	6
Flyers	1	5	6
Training	3	2	5
Social media	2	2 - 0 new	2
Web-site	2	5 - 3 new	5
Communication campaign (e.g radio, TV)	3	2	5
Participation to a conference	48	83	131
Participation to a workshop	22	108	130
Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop	12	9	21
Video/film	2	11	13
Pitch event		1	1
Trade fair	1	0	1
Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	6	22	28
Other		6	6

Social Media are Facebook and Twitter; Websites are: ECOPOTENTIAL Website, Newsletter website, (set up in the 1st RP), Ecopotential4schools website, the Pelagos Storymap Website, the Protected Areas from Space (set up during the 2nd RP); those two indicators do not sum up in the 2 reporting period. At present, we have 5 websites and 2 social media.

A further detail of the communication actions implemented is reported in the following table (From Table 1 in C&D Plan – D12.4) and in the list of communication activities in Table 6 of this document.

Table 2: Communication and Dissemination Actions from table 1 of the C&D Plan – D12.4 and their current status of implementation

Action/tool	How to implement	Actions taken	Status of implementation	Further Actions
Project website with sections targeted at different audiences	Maintain and update the website, included its security.	The website is active and updated.	Continuous actions due to maintain and upgrade.	Update continuously and maintain web site security.

Action/tool	How to implement	Actions taken	Status of implementation	Further Actions
Quarterly newsletter	Quarterly issues to be released using a web content management system (e-mailing) and printed versions to be disseminated at conferences and events.	The mailing list is updated and 8 issues have been released both via e-mailing and in printed version.	Continuous actions due for maintenance and upgrading.	Release the newsletter quarterly.
Social Media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter)	Continuous activities to promote the participation of the scientific community.	Facebook and Twitter to be used regularly for advertising about project’s events and Project related Newsletters.	Continuous actions due for maintenance and upgrading	Continuous update and use of the social media. Enforce their use as a mean for disseminating information to the target audience.
Science policy interface and experience sharing events/ communication material	Organize meetings for science and stakeholders communication.	Awareness raising event “Spaced: Using Earth Observations To Protect Natural Landscapes (Photo Exhibition and workshop)” in Brussels, 10 January 2018. Side event organised at GEO Plenary 2017, Washington DC, US.	Events due have been realised	Policy briefing at GEO and at the European Parliament forthcoming
Visual tools put online via YouTube/Vimeo etc.	Disseminate ECOPOTENTIAL to different audiences.	Story maps and video dissemination. ECOPOTENTIAL Simple Show short video displayed during conferences (see the table related conferences/workshop /others) plus a presentation video on CNR WebTV. 9 slideshow videos have been presented at the EUROGEOS	More videos than foreseen have been realised	A short documentary and a short instructional video are planned.

Action/tool	How to implement	Actions taken	Status of implementation	Further Actions
		stand at GEO Plenary 2017, Washington DC, US and are available on the website. One short video regarding the Vlab has been presented at the side event “GEO in action” at GEO Plenary 2017, Washington DC, US. One short video about freshwater has been presented at a science contest.		
Print material (booklets, science papers reprints)	Print and disseminate the project’s outreach material	Leaflet (Italian, English, Spanish), ECOPOTENTIAL calendars and the book “Spaced: Using Earth Observations To Protect Natural Landscapes” have been printed and distributed at several events.	Printed material has been realised	Distribute the printed material at events / meetings
Photo exhibition	Engage and educate with public exhibitions.	Awareness raising event “Spaced: Using Earth Observations To Protect Natural Landscapes (Photo Exhibition 8-12 January 2018 and at the Committee of the Regions (Feb 2018) in Brussels.	Completed	Italian version of the exhibition will be realised. The photo exhibition will travel to other locations.
School workshops	Educate young generation on the importance of nature to prosperous societies.	Established contacts with selected school teacher groups. Demo version of a scientific game released and tested.	One workshop at University of Salento has been completed in May 2018 (educational game competition)	completed

Action/tool	How to implement	Actions taken	Status of implementation	Further Actions
Science-policy study carried out in WP11 with strong communication component	Raise awareness about bottlenecks and gaps in terms of integration of EO tools in decision making and management of PAs.	A comprehensive questionnaire was developed to identify the needs of PA managers for ECOPOTENTIAL research outputs, in close collaboration with assigned ECOPOTENTIAL scientific partners. Results are reported in D11.2.	First part of the study has been completed within D11.2.	D11.2, submitted in November 2016, reports the first results of the assessment. The report served as basis for the meeting with PA staff in May 2017. Final report by month 42.
Project deliverables	Dissemination of results to wider research and practice communities, use and re-use of outputs.	The available deliverable open to the public published on the website, section http://www.ecopotential-project.eu/2015-08-19-15-19-29/deliverables .	Deliverables have been made public in the website. Further actions will follow as scheduled. CORDIS has not published the deliverables.	Upload public deliverables within one month after submission.
Citizen Science actions	Engage public in conducting science that helps the environment.	The milestone M12.4 (methodology for citizen science, implemented in month 18) has been implemented according to WP12 Task 12.3 and D12.9. D12.9 is ready to be submitted.	CS workshops have been organised and the Beta version of the CS App is ready	CS workshops and use in field of the CS App are foreseen during Summer 2018
Scientific Publications on Journals	Disseminate knowledge and results to the scientific community.	Almost 60 open access papers plus about 20 extended abstracts/book chapters have been published up to now.	In progress; a publication repository has been established (PUMA)	Further scientific results have been and will be submitted publication
Presentations at conferences	Disseminate knowledge and results to the scientific community.	The project's outputs have been presented at more than 90 international events during the second reporting period.	Further actions will follow as scheduled	Scientific results will be submitted for presentations and posters by all research partners.

Action/tool	How to implement	Actions taken	Status of implementation	Further Actions
		The project as a whole has been presented at more than 35 events.		
Science schools	Training of young researchers.	2 additional science schools have taken place in La Palma	More schools than foreseen have been organised.	Summer school on Earth Process Dynamics will take place in Gran Paradiso in July 2018
Public Discussion Forum	Position ECO POTENTIAL scientists as leaders in the field, engage and educate members of all sectors, provide a channel for Science-Policy interface.	Participation to many of the several forums. (LTER, LifeWatch, Future Earth, GEO-BON).	Further actions will follow as scheduled	Participation to several forums
ECOPOTENTIAL Virtual Laboratory Platform	Provide open and unrestricted access to interoperable ecosystem Earth	An advanced version has been released at the beginning of 3 rd year	Further actions will follow as scheduled	The final release is foreseen at year 4
Community of practise (CoP)	Develop a link with stakeholders such as PA managers, nature conservation associations, economic sectors and concerned citizen groups.	A 3 days workshop took place in May 2017. Meeting with the PA managers in ECO POTENTIAL. A training week on Remote sensing and modelling has been organised (Pisa, February 2018)	See deliverable D.1.5 Further actions will follow as scheduled.	Completing the establishing the ECO POTENTIAL CoP within GEO (WP1 - Task 1.4)
Internal communications (discussion board, email, teleconferences)	Ensure efficient information exchange, mutual support and foster scientific innovation.	Internal communication has been established, regular meetings are taking place and all the tools have been implemented.	Action completed in the previous report.	Partners responsible of the tasks are organising the internal communication due for sharing the duties.

Action/tool	How to implement	Actions taken	Status of implementation	Further Actions
				Monitor the efficiency of internal communication tools.

3. C&D performance indicators

The number of persons reached by Communication and Dissemination activities has been estimated as reported in the following Table 3, in order to be uploaded in the Participant’s Portal SyGMA technical reporting web site.

Table 3: Estimate of the number of persons reached by communication activities

ACTIVITY	1 st reporting period	2 nd reporting period	NOTES for 2 nd reporting period
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	4010	10190	Estimate: average 200 people per conference, 50 people per workshop and 20 students per summer school
Industry	n.a.	150	50 people per event involving industry
Civil Society	n.a.	n.a.	
General Public	1200	800	4 presentations at Researchers' night - average 200 people per presentation -
Policy Makers	184	360	5% of attendees at conferences (no workshops)+ 3 events attended by an average of 50 policy makers
Media	6992	17859	37*100 from press releases; web: 9328 - newsletter: 450 facebook: 262 twitter: 599 + (915 - 528) Eu-factor video visualisations + video visualisations: 1386 + 620+1027+300
Investors	n.a.	n.a.	
Customers	n.a.	n.a.	
Other	n.a.	n.a.	

Moreover, monitoring of Success of Communication Tools and Strategies has been planned in the Description of Actions and in the Communication and Dissemination Plan using an array of indicators as reported below. The choice of indicators will be revised in the next update of the C&D plan.

Table 4: Communication indicators as from Description of Actions and C&D Plan. Data from Dec 1st 2016 to May 30 2018

Communication Tool	Metric of verification*	Result
Project website with sections targeted at different audiences	Visitors in each part of the site; Number of pages visited; Referral statistics.	The most visited 25 pages gained 53794 views Other relevant statistics: Total number of sessions: 17,211 (9838 users): 16.42% from Italy, 11.22% from Germany, 9.48 from USA, 6.99 from Spain. Page visualisations: 53794; Unique views: 41801 Page/session: 3.13 % new visitors: 82.2% (%returning visitors: 17.8%). For details on the pages' visits: see Chapter 5 of this report.
Quarterly newsletter	Number of non-partner subscriptions for e-delivery.	Total subscribers: in May 2018: 456 – non-partners: 233 (51%) At present, subscriptions are under review due to the application of the GDPR EU Regulation on protection of personal data.
Social Media (Facebook, Linkedin, Twitter)	Number of followers/members; Number of retweets.	Twitter: 599 followers. Overall twitter impressions: 139,456 (2 reporting periods), 2332 engagements and 462 retweets. Facebook: 262 followers and 27,652 reads.
Research brochures / highlights / policy briefs	Number of downloads.	The brochure and other communication documents have been distributed to partners via the internal communication platform and then the partners distributed the brochure via email / facebook pages, so the information that we have from the website is not complete. Anyway, the “brochure” webpage has been visited 964 times since the date of issue (04/07/2016) to Dec. 31 st 2016 and 443 times during the second reporting period. We estimate a download for each visit.
Visual tools put online via YouTube/Vimeo, etc.	Number of views / other online metrics (e.g. average time spent watching).	On Facebook, the ECOPOTENTIAL video reached 1386 people.

Communication Tool	Metric of verification*	Result
		<p>On YouTube, it has been seen 620 times. On Twitter, the video earned 1027 impressions.</p> <p>Other videos, included the videos presented at the GEO Plenary reached more than 300 visualisations on you tube.</p> <p>The EU-Factor video about ECOPOTENTIAL, made during RP 1, reached now 915 visualisations</p>
Print material (booklets, science papers reprints)	Number of print material distributed.	<p>In the second reporting period 1000 further brochures in English and 1000 in Italian have been printed by CNR. 250 brochures in Spanish have been printed by CREAM.</p> <p>CNR printed 500 table calendars and 300 A3 wall calendars</p> <p>CNR and CREAM printed 1100 copies of the booklet “SPACED: Using Earth Observation to Protect National Landscape”</p> <p>This material has been distributed to partners, to protected areas staff and to stakeholders at public events.</p>
Project deliverables	Number of downloads.	<p>Deliverables have been distributed to partners via the internal communication platform, so and the information that we can extrapolate from the website is not complete. Anyway, during the second reporting period the deliverable webpage has been visited 1224 times (it was 1676 times during the first reporting period).</p>
External communications	Number of information events.	See Table 1 reporting communication and dissemination indicators
Internal communications	Participation in Basecamp.	285 people participate to the internal communication platform (Basecamp) (where 235 in the first RP).

Communication Tool	Metric of verification*	Result
(discussion board, mail)		<p>Basecamp hosts the following discussion groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General - Coordination team - Communication team - 12 discussion group (1 for each work package) - other thematic discussion groups <p>in the 2nd reporting period we used Basecamp also for sharing and storing documents available to all partners</p>

4. Social Media activities

The Facebook site of ECOPOTENTIAL is operative since October 5th 2015. Since the end of the first reporting period, it has gained additional 155 followers, which corresponds to an increase of 49%, 2390 engaged users and a total reach of 27.652 reads (Fig.1, Fig.2). Major peaks of user engagement count from 50 to 100 people, and were during the 2nd General Assembly of the Project, at the GEO Plenary meeting in Oct 2017, at the Photo Exhibition in January 2018 as well as the release of audio-visual material like the brochure, official video, among others. So far, the Facebook site does not register negative feedbacks from its fans. The majority of the fans (83%) are located in Europe, primarily in Italy, Germany, Portugal, Spain and Romania. Compared to the previous reporting period this indicates a gain of users mostly in Europe.

Figure 1. Accumulated frequency of “Lifetime Total Likes” and “Daily engaged users” in Facebook. The Likes received reflects the number of followers. The Daily engaged users are the number of people who clicked, liked, commented on or shared ECO POTENTIAL posts on a daily basis. The time period of the graph displays the second reporting period of the project, from 1 December 2016 to 07 May 2018. Major peaks in the activity are visible around the dates of the 2nd General Assembly (May 2017), during the GEO Plenary in Washington (Oct 2017) and announcement and subsequent release of material of the photo exhibition SPACED (November – December 2017)

Figure 2. Daily total reach: a) during the first reporting period and b) during the second reporting period. from 01 December to 07 May 2018. The total reach is the number of unique people who see the content of the Facebook page on a daily basis.

The Twitter account of ECOPOTENTIAL, under the user @ECOPOTENTIALprj, has been active since October 2015. In the last months, over 400 Tweets were posted and gained 599 followers; it has been included in 44 thematic lists by its followers (Fig.3). Overall, tweets have gained 139,456 impressions, 2332 engagements and 462 retweets.

The most important interest, mentioned by 93% of the followers, is science news, followed by biology (77%), and geography (70%). Moreover, a network map indicates that some of the most important connected users to ECOPOTENTIAL are the Eurogeoss initiative, ESA, partnering institutes and researchers, and among the most connected hashtags are #protectedareas and #earthobservation, #H2020 and #SPACED, among others (Fig.4). The large number of tweets in October 2017 refers to the participation of ECOPOTENTIAL to the XIV GEO Plenary meeting in Washington DC, USA.

Figure 3. Number of tweets per month: a) during the first reporting period and 2) during the second reporting period. The peak in October 2017 corresponds to the GEO Plenary meeting

5. Web Site Statistics (2016-2018 – second reporting period)

The first pages of the ECOPOTENTIAL website have been published in August 2015. Until now, 212 pages have been published, about 100 more on the respect of the previous reporting period. During the second reporting period, the pages have been visited at least 16,217 times. During the second reporting period, there have been a total of 39,613 single pages visits. Some data reported in the following table are Joomla modules rather than pages. The 25 most visited pages were:

N.	Page Title	Publication/activation date	Page Views	Unique Page Views	Entrances
1	ECOPOTENTIAL Project	15/08/2015	14555	11242	10709
2	Protected areas	17/09/2015	3422	2388	301
3	Partners	24/08/2015	3280	2649	261
4	Work packages	15/08/2015	3242	2193	196
5	Mission	19/08/2015	2118	1776	187
6	Project meetings	24/08/2015	1454	792	24
7	Storylines	30/05/2016	1398	936	174
8	Deliverables	30/03/2016	1271	1140	158
9	Publications	30/03/2016	1193	1055	166
10	General meetings	24/08/2015	1154	623	26
11	Coordination	19/10/2015	1128	1013	80
12	Contacts	24/08/2015	884	729	73
13	Presentations	06/10/2015	639	569	39
14	SPACED: Using Earth Observations to Protect Natural Landscapes	04/12/2017	544	475	302
15	Brochures	04/07/2016	457	376	65
16	News archive	11/07/2016	453	381	105
17	Search	17/09/2015	413	342	20
18	form	n.a.	394	227	204
19	Scientific Advisors	11/07/2016	380	335	23
20	Ohrid and Prespa	08/11/2016	362	307	218
21	Videos	19/10/2015	315	255	141
22	News Archive	n.a.	312	211	23
23	Camargue	19/10/2015	299	257	137
24	Posters	n.a.	278	256	14
25	Curonian Lagoon	19/08/2015	251	222	99
	All pages		53794	41801	17211

Table 5: First 25 most visited web pages

Comparing this reporting period to the previous ones, it is relevant to note an increasing interest to the project and to the Protected Areas as a whole, instead of any single ones. Indeed, the main page, “ECOPOTENTIAL project”, has been visited 13,675 times.

Here following the previous reporting period for a quick comparison:

N.	Name	Publication date	Visits
1	Partners	24/08/2015	6781
2	Mission	19/08/2015	4285
3	Contacts	24/08/2015	3471
4	Coordination	19/10/2015	2929
5	Presentations	06/10/2015	2654
6	Mediterranean LME	26/08/2015	2542
7	Hardangervidda	24/08/2015	2399
8	Har Negev	20/08/2015	2335
9	La Palma and Caldera de Taburiente	21/08/2015	2154
10	Posters	19/10/2015	1890
11	First ECOPOTENTIAL General Assembly	28/06/2016	1886
12	Storylines	30/05/2016	1886
13	Camargue	24/08/2015	1863
14	Ohrid and Prespa	24/08/2015	1834
15	Scientific Advisors	17/09/2015	1825
16	Gran Paradiso	24/08/2015	1774
17	Publications	30/03/2016	1726
18	Deliverables	30/03/2016	1676
19	European Projects Workshop on Earth observation 2016	09/06/2016	1556
20	Curonian Lagoon	19/08/2015	1529

In the second reporting period (1 December 2016-31 May 2018), the site hosted 16,217 sessions (from 9,238 users) for a total of 50,905 page visits. Other statistics are shown below:

Figure 5: web page visits timeline in the second reporting period

Figure 6: Web site statistics from Google Analytics

The following image and table show the users’ country connections:

Figure 7: Country of access point to website visits

In the following graph, it is possible to view where the traffic comes from:

- Direct: indicates visits where users navigated directly to the URL,
- Organic Search: indicates visits from organic –unpaid– search results,
- Social: indicates visits from social networks: Facebook, Twitter, etc.,
- Referral: traffic where users clicked a link from another site, excluding major search engines.

Figure 8: point of origin of website search. Organic search means search from search engines (e.g. google)

Organic search continues to be the major source of traffic for the ECOPOTENTIAL website. Direct, referral and social traffic are, as usual, good channels. Here is the list of the first 25 sources:

Source	Sessions	% New sessions
google	8516	48,85%
(direct)	4972	53,24%
t.co (twitter)	146	56,16%
isprambiente.gov.it	109	44,95%
bing	121	33,88%
biogeo.uni-bayreuth.de	137	40,15%
bayceer.uni-bayreuth.de	91	41,76%
uni-bayreuth.de	113	51,33%
facebook.com	167	55,69%
m.facebook.com	65	80,00%
igg.cnr.it	72	38,89%
researchgate.net	67	43,28%
ecopotential-newsletter.igg.cnr.it	70	42,86%
ufz.de	59	55,93%
l.facebook.com	67	68,66%
ecovrp.geodab.eu	212	26,89%
plus.ethz.ch	42	50,00%
ecosia.org	56	32,14%
geo.uni-potsdam.de	56	39,29%
duckduckgo.com	42	50,00%
blog.creaf.cat	27	37,04%
neakriti.gr	28	50,00%
rslab.gr	27	55,56%
centro3a.unitn.it	26	19,23%
outlook.live.com	26	46,15%

Table 6: starting points for access to ECOPOTENTIAL website

We cannot compare this data from Google Analytics with the first reporting period, because the time span monitored in the first reporting period was too short. From the number of users, we can say that the website is accessed by a large number of external users (non partners) with a good bounce rate (Wikipedia reports 60% as average bounce rate). Access is constant during the year with a decrease in August. The peak of accesses in January 2018 is due to the photo exhibition in Bruxelles.

The following figure illustrates the users flow, which confirms that users access the website mostly from the home page.

Figure 9: users flow for access to webpages

The linked website [Protected Areas from Space](http://maps.ecopotential-project.eu) (maps.ecopotential-project.eu, portal to the CREAM server), aimed to allow access to remote sensing maps of the ECOPOTENTIAL protected areas and to extract data and maps, presents the following statistics on access:

The website has been disclosed to the public through the ECOPOTENTIAL website on July 2017. Since then, after the summer break, the number of visits per month has remained pretty constant, with 1007 independent visits and 59,613 executions of the map service, meaning that the service has been provided to be really useful to the scientific community.

Figure 6: number of visits per month, from July 2017 to April 2018

Figure 10: number of executions of the map service

In the following table, the top countries where the visits to the “Protected Areas from Space” service are from:

Country	Count
Spain	222
Italy	217
Germany	129
Portugal	57
Switzerland	36
Belgium	36
United States	32
Netherlands	32
United Kingdom	31
France	25

Table 7: top countries from where the visits to PA from Space come

6. ECOPOTENTIAL Newsletter

The ECOPOTENTIAL Newsletter is released about every four months. It includes articles describing the protected areas and the storylines of the project, abstracts from ECOPOTENTIAL publications or research threads, events within the project, participation at conferences of ECOPOTENTIAL researchers and announcements of other events (usually conferences). Up to now, 8 issues of the Newsletter have been released, 3 of them during the first reporting period and 5 of them during the second reporting period.

The newsletter is released via e-mail through a CMS and also accessible as PDF or posts on the web from the ECOPOTENTIAL website.

The number of subscribers since the first issue has increased from 201 to 445 subscribers.

Overall, the number of readers for each issue is around 40 to 50 % of the subscribers, as it results in the following table, which can be seen as a very good result, as marketing research reveals that an average of 25% of readers of a newsletter is a target result.

Anyway, the comparison of readers of news on social media and newsletter shows that quick communication media as Facebook and Twitter are more efficient because they reach a wider number of users in a short time, and, also, preparing the news for social media is less time-consuming.

Figure 11: readings of the newsletter

7. Attendance at conferences and other dissemination activities.

ECOPOTENTIAL project and its scientific results continue to be presented at a number of scientific and public events. All the events and presentations are listed in Tables 5 and 6 below, grouped in the three major categories:

- Presentations of the project as a whole (in the framework of WP1 – Task 1.3: networking activities)
- Scientific presentations
- Other events and dissemination activities

On the whole, during this second reporting period there have been 90 participation at conferences and 110 at workshops. The project as a whole has been presented 27 times: at 5 scientific conferences and at 22 scientific workshops (all oral presentations). Researchers gave 85 presentations of scientific results at conferences 88 scientific presentations at workshops. ECOPOTENTIAL has also been presented at other events as other projects’ meetings, invited seminars, master courses.

The ECOPOTENTIAL poster “Using remote sensing methods for evaluation of changes in goose feeding areas in Nemunas Delta” was selected as the best poster presentation by the scientific committee of the event “18th Conference of Goose Specialist Group”.

A number of other dissemination activities has been undertaken, as participation at the Researchers’ Night, organization of dedicated workshops, photo exhibitions, press releases, newsletters, videos, and many other web-based communication actions.

Table 7: Summary of presentations at conferences and workshops.

Event	Total	ECOPOTENTIAL as a whole - oral	ECOPOTENTIAL as a whole - poster	Scientific presentations-oral	Scientific presentations-poster
Conferences	83	3	0	59	21
Workshops	108	34	0	68	6
<i>Total ECOPOTENTIAL presentation as a whole</i>		38			
<i>Total ECOPOTENTIAL scientific results presentations</i>				127	27

8. Scientific Publications

From the beginning of the project, a total of 79 peer reviewed articles acknowledging ECOPOTENTIAL have been published. 61 articles have been published on peer reviewed journals, while 18 articles are published as chapter of books or proceedings at conferences (other peer reviewed in the table and chart below).

In Figure 12 the number of papers published per year is shown. 2018 refers to the period January – May, and we expect a larger number of papers in 2018 than in 2017 at the end of the year.

Papers see both the joint collaboration among ECOPOTENTIAL partners among ECOPOTENTIAL scientists with other researchers, meaning that the scope of the research done by partners embraces subjects that are shared also outside the ECOPOTENTIAL community.

Figure 12: Number of peer reviewed publication per year

9. Appendix 1 - ECOPOTENTIAL: Attendance at conferences and workshop

The following table contains a list of:

- A) Oral and poster scientific presentations at conferences
- B) Oral and poster scientific presentations at workshops
- C) Oral and poster presentations at workshops and conferences of the ECOPOTENTIAL project
- D) Presentations at workshops of joint events with other international projects

LEGEND

Participation to a conference	C
Participation to a workshop	W
Poster presentation	P
Oral presentation	O
Scientific presentation	SP
Presentation of the project as a whole	EW

Table 8. A Scientific presentations at conferences

P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
P	29/05-01/06/2018	SWS 2018 Annual Meeting	Denver, Colorado, USA	G. Lefebvre, L. Redmond, C. Christophe, E. Palazzi, S. et al.	Foreseen impacts of climate change on wetland hydrology in the Mediterranean area

P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
O	16-18/05/2018	International seminar "Integrating ecosystem service concept into spatial planning - for sustainable land-use in grasslands and beyond"	Sigulda, Latvia	Arturas Razinkovas-Baziukas, Alex Zemba, et al.	Applied Framework for the assessing and modelling Ecosystem Services in Lithuanian coastal protected areas
O	15-18/05/2019	4th conference on Conservation Science in the Mediterranean Region	Arles, France	L. Redmond, G. Lefebvre, C. Germain, E. Palazzi et al.	Predicting vulnerability of wetlands to climate change across the Mediterranean area
O	9-10/05/208	Conferenza dell'Istituto sull'Inquinamento Atmosferico del CNR	Roma, Italy	Cristina Tarantino, Maria Adamo, Palma Blonda	Cambiamenti di uso del suolo in aree protette da dati satellitari
O	09-10/05/2018	Conferenza dell'Istituto sull'Inquinamento Atmosferico del CNR	Roma, Italy	Saverio Vicario, Maria Adamo, Cristina Tarantino et al.	An Integrated system for multiscale analysis of Ecosystem functions and services in Protected Areas with EO Data in support to geoss in Ecopotential project
O	04-05/05/2018	AK Biogeography	Bonn, Germany	Alexandra Lawrence, Barbara Zennaro	Diversity of Ecosystem Services across European Protected Areas: The Influence of Protection Status
O	04-05/05/2018	AK Biogeography	Bonn, Germany	Severin Irl, Andreas Schweiger, Samuel Hoffmann et al.	Sukzessionsdivergenz entlang einer 6000-jährigen Chronosequenz von Lavaf läu ß en auf einer semi-ariden ozeanischen Insel
O	04-05/05/2018	AK Biogeography	Bonn, Germany	Dagmar Hanz, Vanessa Cutts, Richard Field, Severin Irl et al	Functional diversity of endemic and non-endemic plants on islands

P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
O	22-26/04/2018	KESA 2017	Athens, Greece	O. Dumitru, G. Schwarz, M. Datcu	Monitoring of Coastal Environments Using Data Mining
O	17-19/04/2018	7th Digital Earth Summit	El-Jadida, Morocco	P. Mazzetti, M. Santoro, S. Nativi	Indicators generation for Sustainable Development Goals: the ECOPOTENTIAL Virtual Laboratory Platform
O	9-13/04/2018	European Geoscience Union EGU 2018	Vienna, Austria	Thomas Dirnböck, EAA	PICO presentation: Post-disturbance ground vegetation effects on carbon sequestration in a temperate forest landscape
P	08–13/04/2018	European Geoscience Union EGU 2018	Vienna, Austria	Antonello Provenzale, Ilaria Baneschi, Stefano Ferraris, Mariasilvia Giamberini, Massimo Guidi, Pietro Mosca, Elisa Palazzi, Maddalena Pennisi, Brunella Raco	Carbon fluxes in high-altitude prairies: results from the Critical Zone Observatory at Nivolet
O	08–12/04/2018	European Geoscience Union EGU 2018	Vienna - Austria	Shayli Dor-Haim	Vegetation patch formation in ancient terraces
	6-10/04/2018	European Cetacean Society Conference	La Spezia, Italy	Francesca Santoro	Protecting marine mammals in crowded waters
O	6-10/04/2018	European Cetacean Society Conference	La Spezia, Italy	Bénédicte Madon	A 21st century approach to managing whales and humans interactions
P	27-30/03/2018	18th Conference of Goose Specialist Group	Klaipėda, Lithuania	K. Kaziukonytė, R. Morkūnė, A. Razinkovas-Baziukas	Using remote sensing methods for evaluation of changes in goose feeding areas in Nemunas Delta

P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
O	20-23/03/2018	8th European Coastal Lagoons Symposium	Athens, Greece	R. Morkūnė, A. Razinkovas-Baziukas	Fish guilds in the coastal Baltic Sea: the application of dual and triple stable isotope analysis
O	20-23/03/2018	8th European Coastal Lagoons Symposium	Athens, Greece	A. Razinkovas-Baziukas, N. Českasova, E. Ivanauskas, et al.	Outlook to the future: will the climatic changes alter the trophic state and fishery of the Baltic coastal lagoon?
O	20-23/03/2018	8th European Coastal Lagoons Symposium	Athens, Greece	E. Ivanauskas, D. Baziuke, V. Andrasunas, A. Razinkovas-Baziukas	Application of Bayesian belief networks to evaluate commercial fish stock response to fish management and environmental changes: Curonian lagoon case
P	20-23/03/2018	8th European Coastal Lagoons Symposium	Athens, Greece	E. Ivanauskas, A. Razinkovas-Baziukas	Commercial and recreational fisheries as ecosystem services in the Curonian lagoon
O	11/03/2018	CIMAS I International Mountain Congress	Granada, Spain	Ricardo Moreno (UGR)	Science-policy-society interface in the context of Global Change
P	11-15/12/2017	AGU Fall Meeting 2017	New Orleans (USA)	ISPRA: Valentini, E., Filipponi, F., Nguyen Xuan, A., Taramelli, A	Demonstration of SST value as EBVs descriptor in the Mediterranean Sea.
P	11-15/12/2017	AGU Fall Meeting 2017	New Orleans (USA)	ISPRA: Taramelli A., Valentini E., Filipponi F., Cappucci S.	Coastal Seabed Mapping with Hyperspectral and Lidar data
O	24/11/2017	Promo vierenden symposium 2017	Osnabrück, Germany	Oskar Kärcher (UP - HS OS)	Vulnerability of European Freshwater Catchments to Climate Change

P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
O	09-10/11/2017	Biodiversität und Klima – Vernetzung der Akteure in Deutschland (Biodiversity and the climate - Linking acting institutions in Germany)	Island of Vilm, Germany	Frank Weiser (UBT)	Forest response along treelines to an <i>Epirrita autumnata</i> outbreak in Abisko, Sweden
O	9 - 13/11/2017	International Biogeographical Society Biennial Meeting	Tucson, Arizona, USA	Severin Irl (UBT), Andreas Schweiger (UBT)	Stepwise climatic filtering: a driver of niche width in plant invasion?
O & PM	06-09/11/2017	The 6th International Conference on Desert, Drylands, and Desertification	Sde Boker, Israel	Arnon Karnieli, BGU	Remote sensing: tools and implications in dryland
O	06-09/11/2017	The 6th International Conference on Desert, Drylands, and Desertification	Sde Boker, Israel	Moshe Shachak, BGU	Does a state change in drylands induces vegetation-patch modifications? A case study of LTER site Park Shaked in the Northern Negev
O	02-03/11/2017	6th International Symposium for Research in Protected Areas 2017	Salzburg, Austria	Ariane Walz / UP	CORINE for large-scale monitoring of PAs in Europe
O	02-03/11/2017	6th International Symposium for Research in Protected Areas 2017	Salzburg, Austria	Luisa Gedon / UP	Remote sensing based comprehensive monitoring of land cover change in protected areas
O	02-03/11/2017	6th International Symposium for Research in Protected Areas 2017	Salzburg, Austria	Samuel Hoffmann/UBT, Carl Beierkuhnlein/ UBT	Uniqueness of Protected Areas based on Priority Species as a Potential Driver of Conservation Strategies in Europe

P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
P	02-03/11/2017	6th International Symposium for Research in Protected Areas 2017	Salzburg, Austria	Pia Eibes/UBT	Endemic vascular plants in the high mountains of the Sierra Nevada National Park (Spain)
P	02-03/11/2017	6th International Symposium for Research in Protected Areas 2017	Salzburg, Austria	David Kienle/UBT	Survival in little? Refugia of high-elevated plants in the Spanish Sierra Nevada
P	02-03/11/2017	6th International Symposium for Research in Protected Areas 2017	Salzburg, Austria	Simona Imperio/CNR	Effects of protection status, climate, and water management of rice fields on long-term population dynamics of herons and egrets in north-western Italy
P	02-03/11/2017	6th International Symposium for Research in Protected Areas 2017	Salzburg, Austria	BANESCHI, I., GIAMBERINI, M.S., VITERBI, R., CERRATO, C., IMPERIO, S., FERRARIS, S. & PROVENZALE, A.	Changes in Alpine grassland of Grand Paradiso National Park (Italy): first results from CO2 fluxes monitoring programme
O	02-03/11/2017	6th International Symposium for Research in Protected Areas 2017	Salzburg, Austria	Ole R. Vetaas/ UIB	The management of wild reindeer (Rangifer tarandus) in Hardangervidda National Park, Norway
O	02-03/11/2017	6th International Symposium for Research in Protected Areas 2017	Salzburg, Austria	Thomas Dirnböck	From long-term ecosystem monitoring to regional modelling of ecosystem function in the National Park Kalkalpen, Austria
O	02-03/11/2017	6th International Symposium for Research in Protected Areas 2017	Salzburg, Austria	Christiaan Hummel, Yolande Boyer, Matthias Jurek, Per Magnus Andresen, Johannes Kobler, Carl Beierkuhnlein, Antonello	Ecosystem Services and Pressures in European Protected Areas: Divergent Views of

P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
				Provenzale, Guy Ziv, Marco Heurich, Georgios Kordelas, Rutger de Wit, Ioannis Manakos, Herman Hummel	Environmental Scientists and Managers
O	02-04/11/2017	XIII international conference 'Space, Ecology, Safety'	Sofia, Bulgaria	Ioannis Manakos (CERTH)	Remotely-Sensed Biodiversity Variables for terrestrial ecosystem monitoring
P	02-03/11/2017	6th International Symposium for Research in Protected Areas 2017	Salzburg, Austria	UB: C. Cazacu, Adamescu M. C.	Ecosystem services provided by the bio-physical structure of natural capital in the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve Romania
P	26-27/10/2017	V Annual Conference of the Italian Society for Climate Sciences	Bologna, Italy	Terzago S., von Hardenberg J., Palazzi E.	The RainFARM stochastic precipitation downscaling method adjusted for climate impact studies in complex topography
O	26-27/10/2017	V Annual Conference of the Italian Society for Climate Sciences	Bologna, Italy	Terzago S., Palazzi E., von Hardenberg J., Provenzale A	The representation of snowpack in climate models: the impact of the horizontal resolution
O	24-28/10/2017	11th International Conference of the African Association of Remote Sensing of the Environment	Kampala, Uganda	Moses Cho, Abel Ramoelo, Dzivha L	Modelling land surface phenology for semi-arid biomes in Southern Africa reveals patterns of tree-grass mosaics
O	22/10/2017	ISWC Vienna S4BioDiv Workshop	Vienna, Austria	Magagna, Barbara	EnvThes and semantic repositories (title needs to be confirmed)
O	04/10/2017	ILTER 2017 annual meeting & LTER France meeting	Nantes, France	Provenzale, Giamberini, Imperio, Marangi et al	Changes in Protected Areas: the ECOPOTENTIAL view

P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
O	03/10/2017	ILTER 2017 annual meeting & LTER France meeting	Nantes, France	Daniel Orenstein (Technion - ITT)	Nature, landscapes and biodiversity: what do the 99% (non-ecologists) think?
O	02/10/2017	ILTER 2017 annual meeting & LTER France meeting	Nantes, France	Mariasilvia Giamberini - CNR	The fate of the iconic Salmo letnica in Lake Ohrid
O	26-30/06/2017	5th Helmholtz Alliance week Remote Sensing and Earth System Dynamics	Garmisch-Partenkirchen, Germany	Ralf Kiese, David Kraus, Edwin Haas (KIT)	Impacts of global change on non-CO2 greenhouse gas sink and source strengths of terrestrial ecosystems
O	25-28/09/2017	Earth Observation Open Science 2017	Frascati, Italy	ISPRA: Filipponi, F., Valentini, E., Taramelli, A.	A Collection Of Data Analytics For Earth Observation Time Series Analysis
P	18 - 23/09/2017	SEH 19th European Congress of Herpetology	Salzburg, Austria	D. Poursanidis (FORTH), N. Chrysoulakis(FORTH)	Topographic factors promoting the distribution of the endemic lizard Podarcis cretensis in Samaria National park
O	11-14/09/2017	SPIE Remote Sensing Conference	Warsaw, Poland	Cristina Domingo	On the interest of the spectral bands in the automatic selection of high quality MODIS data through spatial pattern identification
O	11-14/09/2017	SPIE Remote Sensing Conference	Warsaw, Poland	Reza Bahmanyar (DLR)	Land-Cover Evolution Class Analysis in Image Time Series of Landsat and Sentinel-2 Based on Latent Dirichlet Allocation
O	21-25/08/2017	Tagung für Nachwuchswissenschaftler (Conference for young scientists)	Island of Vilm, Germany	Frank Weiser (UBT)	Forest response along treelines to an Epirrita autumnata outbreak in Abisko, Sweden

P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
		hosted by the german environmental ministry)			
P	23-28/07/2017	IGARSS 2017: IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium	Texas, USA	Mihai Datcu (DLR)	Land-Cover Change Detection using Local Feature Descriptors extracted from Spectral Indices
O	23-27/07/2017	ICCB 2017, 28th International Congress for Conservation Biology	Cartagena de Indias, Colombia	Javier Bustamante, Isabel Afán, David Aragonés (EBD-CSIC)	What can remote sensing do for the conservation of vernal pools on Doñanas aeolian sands?
O	06/07/2017	MARE Conference	Amsterdam, NL	Ziemba	Water Quality Assessment and Aquaculture Through Modeling Translated for End Users
P	04-06/07/2017	Spatial Statistics 2017: One World One health	Lancaster, UK	Cristina Domingo	Comparative analysis of variograms obtained from high quality filtered MODIS spectral bands
O	3-7/10/2017	XVII Congress of the Spanish Association of Remote Sensing	Murcia, Spain	Ricardo Díaz-Delgado	Machine learning algorithms for spectral discrimination of aquatic macrophytes under different conditions characteristic from Doñana marshes
O	27-29/06/2017	MultiTemp 2017 conference	Bruges - Belgium	Federico Filipponi, Emiliana Valentini, Taramelli	Sea Surface Temperature changes analysis, an Essential Climate Variable for Ecosystem Services provisioning
O	27-29/06/2017	MultiTemp 2017 conference	Bruges - Belgium	Mihau, Bustamante, Delgado	Land-Cover Evolution Class in Image Time Series of LandSat and Sentinel-2 Based on Latent Dirichlet Allocation

P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
P	26-30/06/2017	5th Helmholtz Alliance week Remote Sensing and Earth System Dynamics	Garmisch-Partenkirchen, Germany	Lange, Maximilian (UFZ); Doktor, Daniel (UFZ)	Trends in vegetation dynamics for forests in protected areas: examples from EU horizon project 'Ecopotential'.
O	12-16/06/2017	11th Baltic Sea Science Congress	Rostock, Germany	H. Hummel, C. Hummel, A. Razinkovas-Baziukas, R. de Wit, Y. Boyer, et al	“The role of Ecosystem Services and Pressures in Protected Areas: Different views of scientists and PA managers”
P	12-13/05/2017	AK Biogeography	Erlangen, Germany	Frank Weiser (UBT)	Forest response along treelines to an <i>Epirrita autumnata</i> outbreak in Abisko, Sweden
P	12-13/05/2017	AK Biogeography	Erlangen, Germany	Esther Baumann (UBT)	Leaf coloration change along an elevational gradient on La Réunion
O	12-13/05/2017	AK Biogeography	Erlangen, Germany	Severin Irl (UBT), Fabian Spaich (UBT), Carl Beierkuhnlein (UBT)	Schatzinsel in Gefahr? Wie der Klimawandel endemische Pflanzenarten in einem ozeanischen Biodiversitätshotspot gefährdet
O	8-12/05/2017	37th International Symposium on Remote Sensing of Environment	Pretoria, South Africa	Abel Ramoelo, Moses A. Cho, Mathieu R, Main R, Naidoo L, Dziba L	Does the integration of optical and synthetic aperture radar (SAR) improves herbaceous biomass estimation using Sentinel-1 and 2 in the savanna ecosystem, South Africa?
O	8-12/05/2017	37th International Symposium on Remote Sensing of Environment	Pretoria, South Africa	Abel Ramoelo, Moses A. Cho, Cecilia Masemola, Dziba L	Estimation of grass nitrogen concentration using the inversion of PROSAIL radiative transfer

P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
					model – in the heterogeneous savanna ecosystem – towards season independent and regional approach
O	8-12/05/2017	37th International Symposium on Remote Sensing of Environment	Pretoria, South Africa	Moses Cho, Abel Ramoelo, Dzivha L	Optimal phenological period for estimating woody cover using MODIS imagery
O	8-12/05/2017	37th International Symposium on Remote Sensing of Environment	Pretoria, South Africa	Renaud Mathieu, Russell Main, Laven Naidoo, Hannah Yang	Potential of Sentinel-1 C-band for discriminating fire scars in deciduous southern African savannahs
O	8-12/05/2017	37th International Symposium on Remote Sensing of Environment	Pretoria, South Africa	Mathieu Renaud, Main Russell, Naidoo Laven, Wessels Konrad, Smit Izak, Asner Greg	Woody resources and land management in the South African Lowveld with L-band SAR and LiDAR imagery
O	8-12/05/2017	37th International Symposium on Remote Sensing of Environment	Pretoria, South Africa	Main, R., Mathieu, R., Cho, M., Kleynhans, W., Wessels, K., Naidoo, L., Asner, G.P.	Application of a semi-empirical model in the estimation of savanna biomass, using hyper-temporal C-band SAR data
O	23–28/04/2017	European Geoscience Union EGU 2017	Vienna, Austria	Silvia Terzago, Elisa Palazzi, Jost von Hardenberg	A simple method to include complex orography in the RainFARM stochastic precipitation downscaling method for climate studies
O	23–28/04/2017	European Geoscience Union EGU 2017	Vienna, Austria	Silvia Terzago, Elisa Palazzi, Jost von Hardenberg	The representation of snow in the EC-Earth climate model: the impact of horizontal resolution

P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
O	23–28/04/2017	European Geoscience Union EGU 2017	Vienna, Austria	Antonello Provenzale, Carl Beierkuhnlein, Mariasilvia Giamberini, et al.	Volcanic supersites as cross-disciplinary laboratories
P	23–28/04/2017	European Geoscience Union EGU 2017	Vienna, Austria	ISPRA: Valentini, E., Nguyen Xuan, A., Filipponi, F., Taramelli, A.	Coastal vulnerability assessment using Fuzzy Logic and Bayesian Belief Network approaches. EGU General Assembly
O	19-21/04/2017	Macro2017	Vienna, Austria	Severin Irl, Andreas Schweiger, Manuel Steinbauer et al.	Hierarchical climatic filtering: towards a mechanistic concept of plant invasion on islands
P	11/04/2017	18th Swiss Global Change Day	Bern, Switzerland	Jonathan Giezendanner, EPFL	Extinction dynamics of mountainous species under climate change
P	20-23/03/2018	8th European Coastal Lagoons Symposium	Athens, Greece	E. Ivanauskas, A. Razinkovas-Baziukas	Commercial and recreational fisheries as ecosystem services in the Curonian lagoon
O	14-16/03/2017	WorldCover 2017 Conference	Frascati, Italy	Richard Lucas, Anthea Mitchell, Palma Blonda, et al.	Global to Local Land Cover and Habitat Mapping: The Ecopotential Approach
O	7-8/03/2017	ECRA General Assembly 2017	Brussels, Belgium	Oskar Kärcher (UP - HS OS)	-

Table 8.B - Scientific Presentations at Workshops

P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
O	16-20/04/2018	The Southern African Science Service Centre for Climate Change and Adaptive Land Management (SASSCAL) symposium	Lusaka, Zambia	Abel Ramoelo, Moses Cho, Renaud Mathieu, Sabelo Madonsela, Nokuthula Mahlangu (CSIR)	Mapping essential biodiversity variables using advanced remote sensing: An overview
P	16-20/04/2018	The Southern African Science Service Centre for Climate Change and Adaptive Land Management (SASSCAL) symposium	Lusaka, Zambia	Abel Ramoelo, Moses Cho (CSIR)	Explaining the spatial distribution of the leaf nitrogen concentrations in semi-arid environments using spectrometer data
O	16-20/04/2018	The Southern African Science Service Centre for Climate Change and Adaptive Land Management (SASSCAL) symposium	Lusaka, Zambia	Moses A. Cho, Abel Ramoelo (CSIR)	Rapid method for assessing bush encroachment using MODIS sensor data
O	7-8/04/2018	6th GEOGLAM RAPP Rangelands and Pasture Productivity and SDG Workshop	Lusaka, Zambia	Abel Ramoelo	EO based estimation of grass quality and quantity: use of the Sentinel constellation
P	03-05/04/2018	2018 NASA LCLUC Spring Science Team Meeting	Gaithersburg, USA	Ioannis Manakos	'The EODESM system: a New Approach to Land Cover and Change Classification' (short talk with poster) & 'GOF-C-GOLD SCERIN: Multinational Intercomparison of Global and Continental Land Cover Products in South Central and Eastern European Region - preliminary results' (poster)

P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
O	20-24/03/2018	International Biogeographical Society meeting: Climate Change Biogeography	Évora, Portugal	Beierkuhnlein, C ; Hoffmann, S; Hanz, D; Kienle et al.	Challenges for Networks of Protected Areas in a Rapidly Changing Climate
O	20-24/03/2018	International Biogeographical Society meeting: Climate Change Biogeography	Évora, Portugal	Kienle, D (UBT); Hanz, D; Irl, S; Steinbauer, M; Weiser, F; Beierkuhnlein, C	Precipitation changes on oceanic islands – new insights to assess diversity and endemism
P	6-9/03/2018	Mediterranean Desert Margin and Drylands Workshop	Leipzig, Germany		Extraction of plant phenological metrics from EO satellite data and their potential for climate and land-use change depiction.
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	Ioannis Manakos (CERTH)	Hydroperiod & Vegetation Analysis training sessions
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	D. Poursanidis (FORTH), A. Tsakirakis (Samaria NP-FORTH)	Lectures on: a) Thermal data: Land surface temperature and b) In-situ data needs - metadata
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	Yaniss Guigoz (UNIGE&GRID-Geneva)	VLab Platform - GEO/GEOSS introduction
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	Felix Greifeneder, Ruth Sonnenschein (Eurac)	Remote sensing of water resources in mountain areas
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	Valentini, E., Filipponi, F., Nguyen Xuan, A., Taramelli, A.	Food provision & Biodiversity: Temperature trends in open waters

P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
	5-9/02/2018	GobDiversity Workshop: Informing Species Distribution Models and Essential Biodiversity Variables using Remote Sensing	Zürich, Switzerland	Thomas Dirnböck, EAA	Oral presentation: Contribution of Long-Term Ecological Research and the Ecopotential project to advancing Essential Biodiversity Variables and Remote Sensing
O	09-11/01/2018	SPACED: Using Earth Observation to Protect Natural Landscapes	Brussels, Belgium	Claudia Notarnicola (Eurac)	Challenges in observing mountain ecosystems
O	08-09/12/2017	Italy in US - INGV, ISPRA, and USGS science exchange in Louisiana - under the bilateral agreements Italy - US	Lafayette & New Orleans (USA)	ISPRA: Valentini, E., Nguyen, Xuan, A., Filipponi F. & Taramelli, A.	Ecosystem services for coastal protection using EO: flood regulation and erosion prevention studies & notes
P	21/11/2017	Citizen science Workshop	Roma, Italy	Orhideja Tasevska, Elizabeta Veljanoska Sarafiloska - HIO	PA Ohrid/Prespa lakes
O	23/10/2017	GEO Plenary meeting 2017 - Side event GEO in ACTION	Washington DC, USA	Palma Blonda (CNR-IIA), Paolo Mazzetti (CNR-IIA)	From Data to Knowledge: Biodiversity and Ecosystem - the Ecopotential scenario
O	23-27/10/2017	GEO Plenary meeting 2017	Washington DC, USA	Marc Zebisch - EURAC	European Mountains - EO for environmental monitoring in mountains – opportunities and challenges (e' questo il titolo?)
O	23-27/10/2017	GEO Plenary meeting 2017 - Side event EUROGEOS	Washington DC, USA	Max Craglia	EUROGEOS Protected Areas pilot
O	23-27/10/2017	GEO Plenary meeting 2017 - Side event EUROGEOS	Washington DC, USA	Joan Maso - CREAM	EUROGEOS

P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
O	25-28/09/2017	Earth Observation Open Science 2017	Frascati, Italy	Stefano Nativi, Paolo Mazzetti, Mattia Santoro et al.	The GEO ECOPOTENTIAL Virtual Laboratory: a virtual research environment for ecosystem open science
O	12-14/09/2017	Education in Earth Observation for Bulgarian Secondary Schools' workshop & summer school	Blagoevgrad, Bulgaria	Ioannis Manakos (CERTH)	Contribution of EO to Environmental Education (workshop pres), The Food and Agricultural Organisation (FAO) Land Cover Classification System (LCCS2) & Application of Earth Observation in ecosystem services (summer school pres)
	07-08/09/2017	Workshop for Prioritizing Essential Biodiversity Variables derived from EO	Enschede, Netherlands	Geijzendorffer, Ilse (TdV)	Participation in an interactive workshop of GEO BON and the Globdiversity project
O	10-11/7/2017	45th Annual Meeting of the Israel Union of Ecology and Environmental Sciences	Herzlia, Israel	Miri Tsalyuk, Idan Porat, Daniel Orenstein (Technion - ITT)	Perspectives on landscapes, nature and environment among residents and visitors to the Negev Highlands
O	19/06/2017	European GEO Workshop – EGW 2017	Helsinki, Finland	Elisa Palazzi (CNR)	Elevation Dependent Warming and the need for a network of monitoring stations: the role of GEO GNOME
O	19-21/06/2017	European GEO Workshop – EGW 2017	Helsinki, Finland	Francisco Bonnet Garcia - University of Grenada	Blending Remote Sensing and Earth Observation at Sierra Nevada National Park, Spain

P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
O	08/06/2017	ETH D-BAUG workshop "Natural Hazards"	Zürich, Switzerland	Ana Stritih (ETH)	"Quantifying avalanche protection in forests using remote sensing"
O	02-05/05/2017	Workshop "Application of Earth Observation tools in protected areas"	Pisa, Italy	Ioannis Manakos (CERTH), Cristina Domingo (CREAF), Palma Blonda (CNR)	Applications of EO tools in Protected Areas Workshop (presentation)
O	02-05/05/2017	The International Workshop on Knowledge Extraction and Semantic Annotation	Pisa, Italy	Arnon Karnieli, BGU	Remote sensing: Har HaNegev
O	02-05/05/2017	Workshop "Application of Earth Observation tools in protected areas"	Pisa, Italy	Poulin, Brigitte, Geijzendorffer, Ilse et al.	Camargue
O	02-05/05/2017	Workshop "Application of Earth Observation tools in protected areas"	Pisa, Italy	H. Hummel, C. Hummel (oral presentations)	"Variation in perspectives of Protected Area managers and scientists on the use of factors for Ecosystem Services, Ecosystem Functions and Structures, and Pressures"
O	02-05/05/2017	Workshop "Application of Earth Observation tools in protected areas"	Pisa, Italy	H. Hummel, C. Hummel (oral presentations)	"Breakout sessions: Matching perspectives of PA managers and scientists"
	02-05/05/2017	Workshop "Application of Earth Observation tools in protected areas"	Pisa, Italy	D. Poursanidis (FORTH), A. Barnias (Samaria NP)	In situ data - Identification of the needs for the use of in situ data
P	12-17/03/2017	15th Annual Savanna Science Networking Meeting	Skukuza, South Africa	Abel Ramoelo, Simona Imperio, Moses Cho, Antonello Provenzale, Izak Smit	Analysis of temporal changes in climate and grass biomass in and around Kruger National Park

P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
O & P	9-10/03/2017	Workshop "Möglichkeiten und Herausforderungen im Kontext aktueller und zukünftiger Erdbeobachtungsdaten"	Leipzig, Germany	Lange, Maximilian (UFZ); Benjamin Dechant (UFZ); Doktor, Daniel (UFZ)	Challenges & opportunities in the light of current and upcoming satellite missions; Validation of Sentinel-2 products based on continuous spectral measurements.
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	Joaquim Alonso (InBIO/ICETA)	Documentation of data quality requirements
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	Pedro Castro (InBIO/ICETA)	Development of data quality evaluation routines - THEMatic Metadata-based and fitness for use Spatial data quality Evaluation: ThemisE platform
O	14-15/02/2017	Netherlands Annual Ecology Meeting (NAEM 2017)	Lunteren, Netherlands	H. Hummel, C. Hummel, Y. Boyer, R. de Wit, et al. (oral presentation), C. Hummel (chair for Parallel session 2a)	"The role of Ecosystem Services in Protected Areas"
O	14-15/02/2017	Netherlands Annual Ecology Meeting (NAEM 2017)	Lunteren, Netherlands	H. Hummel, C. Hummel, Y. Boyer, R. de Wit, et al. (oral presentation), C. Hummel (chair for Parallel session 2a)	The effectiveness of the Ecosystem Services approach"
O	02-05/05/2017	Workshop "Application of Earth Observation tools in protected areas"	Pisa, Italy	Hummel H.	Variation in perspectives of Protected Area managers and scientists on the use of factors for Ecosystem Services: Functions and Pressures

P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
O	02-05/05/2017	Workshop “Application of Earth Observation tools in protected areas”	Pisa, Italy	Imperio S.	Setting the stage: Presentation of case studies of good practice of the use of EO tools for the management of Protected Areas.
O	02-05/05/2017	Workshop “Application of Earth Observation tools in protected areas”	Pisa, Italy	Domingo C., Poursanidis D.	Presentation of current and future application of Remote Sensing and in situ data in Protected Areas, with technical specifications and application for management and conservation
O	02-05/05/2017	Workshop “Application of Earth Observation tools in protected areas”	Pisa, Italy	Bergmann T.	Breakout sessions: Remote Sensing - Identification of the needs for the use of Remote Sensing including EO training needs.
O	02-05/05/2017	Workshop “Application of Earth Observation tools in protected areas”	Pisa, Italy	Group facilitators: Marine/coastal: Ioannis Manakos (CERTH) and Andrea Taramelli (ISPRA). Terrestrial ecosystems: Cristina Domingo (CREAF) Arnon Karnieli (BGU) and Peres Serra (UAB)/Har HaNegev	Remote Sensing - Identification of the needs for the use of Remote Sensing including EO training needs.
O	02-05/05/2017	Workshop “Application of Earth Observation tools in protected areas”	Pisa, Italy	Hummel H.	Matching perspectives of PA managers and scientist

P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
O	02-05/05/2017	Workshop “Application of Earth Observation tools in protected areas”	Pisa, Italy	Provenzale A., Geijzendorffer I.	Towards an Ecosystem Community of Practice, including overall training needs and the science-policy interface
O	02-05/05/2017	Workshop “Application of Earth Observation tools in protected areas”	Pisa, Italy	Provenzale A.	Presentation on EO based ecosystem modelling
O	02-05/05/2017	Workshop “Application of Earth Observation tools in protected areas”	Pisa, Italy	Bonn A., Mantel M., Orenstein D. et al.	Presentation on possibilities and issues for participatory ES Mapping & Citizen Science in Protected Areas
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	Arnon Karnieli and Micha Silver	Principles / basics of Remote sensing
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	Joan Masó	ECOPOTENTIAL map browser overview
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	Joan Masó	Retrieval, Preprocessing and coregistration of Optical data
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	Manakos I.	Hydroperiod & Vegetation Analysis training sessions
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	Felix Greifeneder / R. Sonnenchein	Remote sensing of water resources in mountain areas

P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	F.Filipponi - A. Nguyen Xuan E. Valentini	Biodiversity, food provision, temperature, chlorophyll
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	Arnon Karnieli and Micha Silver	Advanced Time series analysis, Land
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	Dimitris Poursanidis	Thermal data: Land surface temperature
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	Joan Masó	Exploring data products using the ECOPotencial Web browser
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	Ioannis Manakos	Vegetation analysis
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	Richard Lucas	The Earth Observation Data for EcoSystem Monitoring (EODESM)
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	Ghada El Serafy	Discussion about modelling needs
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	A. Ziemba, Ghada El Serafy	Remote Sensing Modelling – Validation
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	D. Poursanidis	In-situ data needs - metadata

P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	J. Peterseil	Metadata provision and hands on exercise with DEIMS-SDR
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	J. Peterseil	Data discovery and visualisation of in-situ data
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	Alonso J.	Access to in situ data: Documentation of data quality requirements
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	Castro P.	Access to in situ data: hands on exercise with ThemisE
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	J. Petersails	Access to in situ data: Feedback on training and discussion
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	A. Ziemba, Ghada El Serafy	Correlation Models and Empirical methods
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	Imperio S.	Statistical Models
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	Yannis Guigoz - P.Mazzetti M. Santoro	Virtual Lab Platform and GEO/GEOS
O	19-23/02/2018	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	Runa Lindebjerg	Design of the instructional video for Protected Areas staff

P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
O	30/05/2018	Conferenza dell'Istituto di geoscienze e georisorse	Pisa, Italy	Silvia Giamberini Ilaria Baneschi Pietro Mosca - CNR	Flussi di CO2 e studio della zona critica nel Parco Nazionale del Gran Paradiso

Table 8-C: General Presentations of the ECOPOTENTIAL Project at Conferences and Workshops WorkPakage 12.1 (dissemination) + 1.4 (networking)

Event Type	P /O	DATE	kind of presentation (scientific/non scientific)	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
W	O	02-04/05/2018	EW	3rd GEO Data Providers Workshop	Frascati, Italy	P. Mazzetti , I. Manakos, M. Santoro, P. Blonda et al.	Ecopotential
W		08 - 09/11/2017	EW	EcoPotential WP9 storyline workshop with stakeholders	Gerês, Portugal	Cláudia Carvalho-Santos, António Monteiro and Salvador Arenas-Castro (InBIO/ICETA)	Stakeholders meeting
W	O	24/10/2017	EW	EO for achieving & monitoring mountain-related SDGs: ECOPOTENTIAL, GEO-GNOME & GEO-ECO Side Event to GEO Plenary XIV 2017	Washington DC, USA	Ioannis Manakos (CERTH)	Overview of ECOPOTENTIAL project

Event Type	P /O	DATE	kind of presentation (scientific/non scientific)	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
W	O	24/10/2017	EW	EO for achieving & monitoring mountain-related SDGs: ECOPOTENTIAL, GEO-GNOME & GEO-ECO Side Event to GEO Plenary XIV 2017	Washington DC, USA	Elisa Palazzi (CNR)	GNOME and GEO-ECO
W		23-27/10/2017	EW	GEO Plenary meeting 2017	Washington DC, USA	Joan Maso - CREAM	ECOPOTENTIAL presentation at "GEO in ACTION" (GCI for Biodiversity" 2/2 Ecopotential) – 23 Ottobre ore 15 :00
W	O	20-23/06/2017	EW	SCERIN-5 PECS Hungary	Pecs, Hungary	Ioannis Manakos (CERTH)	EOs improving ecosystem benefits: ECOPOTENTIAL Activities in the SCERIN Protected Areas
W	O	19-21/06/2017	EW	European GEO Workshop – EGW 2017	Helsinki, Finland	Mariasilvia Giamberini - CNR	Geosphere-Biosphere Interactions in Mountain Protected Areas: the ECOPOTENTIAL View
W	O	19-21/06/2017	EW	European GEO Workshop – EGW 2017	Helsinki, Finland	Joan Maso - CREAM	Protected Areas from Space: the ECOPOTENTIAL View
C	O	23-28/04/2017	EW	European Geoscience Union EGU 2017	Vienna, Austria	Antonello Provenzale, Silvia Giamberini, Carl Beierkuhnlein, Arnon Karnieli, Carmela Marangi	Geosphere-biosphere interactions in European Protected Areas: a view from the H2020 ECOPOTENTIAL Project
W	O	05-07/04/2017	EW	Climateurope Festival 2017	Valencia, Spain	Ioannis Manakos (CERTH)	ECOPOTENTIAL: Remote sensing for ecosystems

Event Type	P /O	DATE	kind of presentation (scientific/non scientific)	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
C	O	14-16/03/2017	EW	EU BON Final Meeting	Brussels, Belgium	Carl Beierkuhnlein, Samuel Hoffmann, Antonello Provenzale	ECOPOTENTIAL - Protected Areas in a Continental Perspective
C	O	7-8/03/2017	EW	ECRA General Assembly 2017	Brussels, Belgium	Antonello Provenzale	Geosphere-biosphere-hydrosphere interactions in the earth critical zone - lessons from European Protected Areas and the H2020 ECOPOTENTIAL project
W	O	02-05/05/2017	EW	Workshop “Application of Earth Observation tools in protected areas”	Pisa, Italy	Schoolmeester T.	Communicating ECOPOTENTIAL – The use of story maps and the upcoming photo exhibition
W	O	02-05/05/2017	EW	Workshop “Application of Earth Observation tools in protected areas”	Pisa, Italy	Provenzale A.	Summary of results and requirements on EO-based modelling tools in Protected Areas, including training needs and perspectives
W	O	19-21/06/2017	EW	European GEO Workshop – EGW 2017	Helsinki, Finland	Antonello Provenzale - CNR	Geosphere-biosphere interactions and ecosystem changes from space: the ECOPOTENTIAL view
W	O	30/05/2018	EW	Conferenza dell’Istituto di Geoscienze e Georisorse	Pisa, Italy	Silvia Giamberini Antonello Provenzale - CNR	ECOPOTENTIAL: usare i dati di osservazione della Terra per lo studio degli ecosistemi naturali

TABLE 8-D-Presentations at workshops of joint events with other international projects

Event Type	P /O	DATE	kind of presentation (scientific/non scientific)	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
JA		07-08/5/2018	EW	Dissemination activities about Ecopotential outcomes to other, similar, EU funded projects like EcoSUSTAIN	Sibenik, Croatia	Ioannis Dontas	General discussion on Ecopotential outcomes and uses to an audience of National Parks
JA		15/11/2017	EW	Dissemination activities about Ecopotential outcomes to other, similar, EU funded projects like EcoSUSTAIN	Athens, Greece	Ioannis Dontas (ARATOS)	General discussion on Ecopotential outcomes and uses to an audience of National Parks
JA		16-20/01/2017	EW	ECOPOTENTIAL-SWOS joint meeting	Arles, France	Ioannis Manakos (CERTH)	Participation to the meeting (no presentation)
JA		16-19/01/2017	EW	ECOPOTENTIAL-SWOS joint meeting	Arles, France	UNEP-WCMC	Participation to the meeting (no presentation)
JA	O	16-19/01/2017	EW	ECOPOTENTIAL-SWOS joint meeting	Arles, France	H. Hummel, C. Hummel, Y. Boyer, R. de Wit, et al. (oral presentation)	"Future Protected Areas and extensions beyond the boundaries of PAs: Points of view of different stakeholders"
W / JA		16-20/01/2017	EW	ECOPOTENTIAL-SWOS joint meeting	Arles, France	Provenzale.	ECOPOTENTIAL: Improving future ecosystem benefits through Earth Observations
W / JA	O	16-19/01/2017	EW	ECOPOTENTIAL-SWOS joint meeting	Arles, France	Mariasilvia Giamberini - CNR	Ecosystem services and biodiversity crisis across mountain lakes: Lake Ohrid - FYROM
W / JA	O	16-19/01/2017	EW	ECOPOTENTIAL-SWOS joint meeting	Arles, France	Mariasilvia Giamberini - CNR	ECOPOTENTIAL: a "connected" community

Event Type	P /O	DATE	kind of presentation (scientific/non scientific)	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
W & V/F	O	01/01/2017	EW	Copernicus User Uptake Information Sessions	Athens, Arhus, other EU countries	ISPRA: Valentini, E., Taramelli, A., Nguyen Xuan, A. et al.	Coastal Vulnerability assessment
W &V/F	O	01/01/2017	EW	Copernicus User Uptake Information Sessions	Athens, Arhus, other EU countries	ISPRA: Valentini, E., Taramelli, A., Nguyen Xuan, A. et al.	ISPRA: Food provision & Aquaculture assessments
W / JA	O	16-18/01/2017	EW	ECOPOTENTIAL-SWOS joint meeting	Arles, France	Provenzale A.	Introduction to the project, its approach and structure
W / JA	O	16-18/01/2017	EW	ECOPOTENTIAL-SWOS joint meeting	Arles, France	Domingo C.	A Remote Sensing view of PAs from space: available results on satellite observations for Pas
W / JA	O	16-18/01/2017	EW	ECOPOTENTIAL-SWOS joint meeting	Arles, France	Provenzale A.	Characterizing changes in PAs and future projections
W / JA	O	16-18/01/2017	EW	ECOPOTENTIAL-SWOS joint meeting	Arles, France	El Serafy G.	Data assimilation and uncertainty: example of the Wadden Sea
W / JA	O	16-18/01/2017	EW	ECOPOTENTIAL-SWOS joint meeting	Arles, France	Provenzale A.	Perspectives (Cross-scale interactions, Earth Critical Zone)
W / JA	O	16-18/01/2017	EW	ECOPOTENTIAL-SWOS joint meeting	Arles, France	Hummel H.	Future Protected Areas and extensions beyond the boundaries of PAs
W / JA	O	16-18/01/2017	EW	ECOPOTENTIAL-SWOS joint meeting	Arles, France	Giamberini S.	Dissemination activities
W / JA	O	16-18/01/2017	EW	ECOPOTENTIAL-SWOS joint meeting	Arles, France	Ziv G.	Storyline examples: Sierra Nevada and HarHaNegev
W / JA	O	16-18/01/2017	EW	ECOPOTENTIAL-SWOS joint meeting	Arles, France	Giamberini S.	Storyline examples: Orhid and Prespa Lakes

Event Type	P /O	DATE	kind of presentation (scientific/non scientific)	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
W / JA	O	16-18/01/2017	EW	ECOPOTENTIAL-SWOS joint meeting	Arles, France	Guerra C.	Analysis of the Essential Variables used in the Storylines
W / JA	O	01-05/10/2017	EW	Toward a unified framework for life supporting systems in the Anthropocene	Tsuba, Israel	Moshe Shachak	Life Supporting System in the Anthropocene
W / JA	O	01-05/10/2017	EW	Toward a unified framework for life supporting systems in the Anthropocene	Tsuba, Israel	Meuron E.	Modelling of Ecological Integrity as an integrated tool for linking Ecological Integrity dimensions
W / JA	O	01-05/10/2017	EW	Toward a unified framework for life supporting systems in the Anthropocene	Tsuba, Israel	Orenstein D.	Stakeholder perceptions of Ecological Services and their links to ecosystem functions
W / JA	O	01-05/10/2017	EW	Toward a unified framework for life supporting systems in the Anthropocene	Tsuba, Israel	Avni N.	The challenge of Ecological Services in water limited life supporting systems
W / JA	O	01-05/10/2017	EW	Toward a unified framework for life supporting systems in the Anthropocene	Tsuba, Israel	Karnieli A.	Remote sensing monitoring of human-induced changes in drylands ecosystems
W / JA	O	01-05/10/2017	EW	Toward a unified framework for life supporting systems in the Anthropocene	Tsuba, Israel	Provenzale A.	Climate change as a main driving force of Life Supporting System dynamics in the Anthropocene
W / JA	O	01-05/10/2017	EW	Toward a unified framework for life supporting systems in the Anthropocene	Tsuba, Israel	Orenstein D.	Human interactions with the critical zone toward ecological integrity in the Anthropocene

10. Appendix 2 – Other dissemination events and actions

The following table contains a list of:

- A) DISSEMINATION ON MAGAZINES, PRESS RELEASES, NEWSLETTERS, NON SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS
- B) ORGANISATION OF EVENTS AND WORKSHOPS
- C) SOCIAL MEDIA AND WEBSITE MANAGEMENT
- D) EXHIBITIONS
- E) FLYERS
- F) OTHER DISSEMINATION EVENTS

LEGEND

Organisation of a workshop	PMW
Press release	PR
Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)	NS/NP
Exhibition	E
Flyers	F
training	T
Social media	SM
Web-site	WEB
Communication campaign (e.g radio, TV)	CC
Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop	EO
Video/film	V/F
Pitch event	PE
Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	JA
Other	O

TABLE 9-A: Dissemination on magazines, press releases, newsletters, non scientific publications

Event Type	P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
PR		02/05/2018	Press release on the Pisa training week	Pisa, Italy	Magnus Andresen, UN Environment	Earth Observation technology offers new opportunity to assess threats to European Protected Areas
NS/NP		01/04/2018	Article on the Magazine of Gran Paradiso National Park	Torino, Italy	Mariasilvia Giamberini and Antonello Provenzale - CNR	I PARCHI NATURALI VISTI DAI SATELLITI
PE		20/03/2018	CPH:DOX Science Film Forum Research Projects 2018	Copenhagen, Denmark	Mariasilvia Giamberini and Asja Bernd - CNR	SPACED: protecting nature through Earth observation
NS/NP		18/03/2018	Article on popular science magazine FOCUS	Italy	Mariasilvia Giamberini - CNR	Le sentinelle del pianeta (In Italian)
PR		17/03/2018	press releases CNR	Copenhagen, Denmark	Giamberini S. Asja Bernd A., Provenzale A.	CPH:DOX - Science Film Forum Research Projects 2018
PR		14/03/2018	Press release Committee of the Regions	Brussels, Belgium	Magnus Andresen, UN Environment	SPACED exhibition at the EU Committee of the Regions
PR		12/03/2018	Post on Web EBD-CSIC publication PLoS ONE 13(2): e0192702	Seville, Spain	Giulia Crema EBD-CSIC	Como afectará el cambio climático a las aves acuáticas (How will climate change affect endangered Mediterranean waterbirds)
CC		05/03/2018	Interview to national radio statio "LRT radijas"	Lithuania	Arturas Razinkovas-Baziukas	Interview about evaluation of ecosystem services in Lithuania coastal zone
PR		27/02/2018	Contribution to an article at the largest internet portal in the Baltic states	Online	Arturas Razinkovas-Baziukas	Bandoma apskaičiuoti Lietuvos gamtos teikiamą naudą
PR		27/02/2018	Press release UNEP		Magnus Andresen - UNEP	Satellites help fight environmental degradation throughout Europe Europe

Event Type	P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
PR		22/02/2018	press releases CNR	Pisa, Italy	Stefania Lombardi - CNR	ECOPOTENTIAL Remote Sensing training week
CC		20/02/2018	interview for a web TV Channel	Pisa, Italy	Mariasilvia Giamberini - CNR	Interview for the CNR web channel regarding the Remote Sensing training
PR		09/02/2018	Launch event SPACED Exhibition	Brussels, Belgium	Bjorn Alfthan - Grid Arendal	Launch event with speeches from high level representatives of the EU Parliament, Commission and the ECOPOTENTIAL project
NS/NP		01/02/2018	Popular science article on the monthly magazine "Montagne 360"	Torino, Italy	Elisa Palazzi (CNR)	Le montagne del futuro
PR		01/02/2018	Press release Committee of the Regions	Brussels, Belgium	Magnus Andresen - UNEP	CoR - SPACED exhibition - Using Earth Observation to protect natural landscapes
PR		03/01/2018	press releases CNR	Roma, Italy	Mariasilvia Giamberini - CNR	Ecopotential al Parlamento Europeo Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
PR		30/12/2017	press releases CNR	Torino, Italy	Angela Franchi (journalist)	Il Politecnico di Milano partner del progetto Ecopotential
NS/NP	O	01/12/2017	ECOPOTENTIAL4SCHOOLS booklet on transitional waters PA	Lecce, Italy	Francesco Cozzoli - UNISALENTO	ECOPOTENTIAL4SCHOOLS An international game experience with students
PR		28/11/2017	press releases CNR	Roma, Italy	Mariasilvia Giamberini and Antonello Provenzale - CNR	Il Cnr coordina il progetto ECOPOTENTIAL per gli ecosistemi
PR		13/11/2017	press releases	Vienna, Austria	Antonello Provenzale - CNR	GeoLog Imaggio on Mondays: Bird's eye view of Trebecchi Lakes
NS/NP		01/07/2017	Ecopotential newsletter article	Peneda-Gerês, Portugal	António Monteiro (InBIO/ICETA)	Estimating invasion of non native trees with satellite data in Protected Areas

Event Type	P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
PR		03/05/2017	press releases	Roma, Italy	ISPRA	Project H2020 ECOPOTENTIAL: "Application of Earth Observation tools in Protected Areas" — English
PR		03/05/2017	training RS Feb 2018 Pisa E press releases CNR	Roma, Italy	Mariasilvia Giamberini e Simona Imperio, CNR	Workshop "Application of Earth Observation tools in protected areas. Establishing a community of practice
PR		03/05/2017	press releases	Trapani, Italy	ISPRA	L'Area Marina Protetta "Isole Egadi" ad Horizon2020 ECOPOTENTIAL
PR		02/05/2017	press releases	Favignana (TP)	ISPRA	L'AMP delle Egadi con l'ENEA al convegno del progetto Horizon2020 Ecopotential illustra i risultati sull'analisi dei dati satellitari per lo studio dei fondali e degli impatti sulla Posidonia
PR		02/05/2017	press releases	Marsala, Italy	ISPRA	Convegno del progetto Horizon2020 Ecopotential: l'Amp delle Egadi con l'Enea
PR		30/04/2017	article on CNR web magazine	Roma, Italy	Mariasilvia Giamberini - CNR	La natura vista dai satelliti (Workshop 'Application of earth observation tools in protected areas in Europe and beyond')
PR		30/04/2017	press releases CNR	Roma, Italy	CNR	La natura vista dai satelliti (Workshop 'Application of earth observation tools in protected areas in Europe and beyond')
PR		28/04/2017	press releases Istituto di Ricerca sul Territorio e l'Ambiente "Leonardo"	Pisa, Italy	CNR	Ecopotential: i satelliti al servizio degli ecosistemi protetti. Workshop a San Rossore, 2-5 maggio 2017
PR		28/04/2017	press releases	Palermo, Italy	CNR	Ambiente, "Sentinel": i satelliti che studiano gli ecosistemi

Event Type	P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
PR		28/04/2017	press releases	Roma, Italy	CNR	La natura vista dallo spazio. 'Sentinel', i satelliti che studiano gli ecosistemi
PR		28/04/2017	press releases	Pisa, Italy	Filomena Fotia (Journalist)	Ambiente, "Sentinel": i satelliti che studiano gli ecosistemi
PR		28/04/2017	press releases	Pisa, Italy	Mariasilvia Giamberini e Simona Imperio, CNR	Ambiente: satelliti per studiare ecosistemi di aree protette
PR		28/04/2017	press releases CNR	Pisa, Italy	CNR	I satelliti per studiare le aree protette Attualità Pisa
PR		28/04/2017	press releases CNR	Roma, Italy	CNR	La natura vista dai satelliti - Parco Naturale Regionale di San Rossore, Pisa 2- 5 Maggio 2017
PR		28/04/2017	press releases	Pisa, Italy	CNR	I satelliti per studiare le aree protette
PR		27/04/2017	press releases	Roma, Italy	CNR	La natura vista dai satelliti (Workshop 'Application of earth observation tools in protected areas in Europe and beyond')
PR		23/02/2017	Post on Web EBD-CSIC publication Sci Adv 3 e1601198 DOI: 10.1126/sciadv.1601198	Seville, Spain	JA	
PR		13/02/2017	Post on Web EBD-CSIC publication Front Ecol Environ doi:10.1002/fee.1459	Seville, Spain	JA / PMW	O
PR		28/12/2016	Newsletter #4	Online	W / JA	O
PR		01/01/2017	press releases	Potzdam, DE	W / JA	O
PR		01/04//2017	Newsletter #5	Online	W / JA	O

Event Type	P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
PR		01/07/2017	Newsletter #6	Online	W / JA	O
PR		01/12/2017	Newsletter #7	Online	W / JA	O
PR		17/04/2018	Newsletter #8	Online	W / JA	O
NS/NP		05/04/2018	Newsletter 8	Pisa, Italy	Silvia Terzago / Elisa Palazzi - CNR	"Snow water equivalent in the Alps as seen by gridded data sets, CMIP5 and CORDEX climate models", from article by Terzago, S., von Hardenberg, J., Palazzi, E., and Provenzale, A. The Cryosphere, 11, 1625-1645
NS/NP		05/04/2018	Newsletter 8	Pisa, Italy	Thomas Dirnböck, EAA	"Climate change may improve forest ecosystem's capacity to retain excessive airborne Nitrogen", from the article: Historic nitrogen deposition determines future climate change effects on nitrogen retention in temperate forests. Dirnböck, T., Foldal, C., Djukic, I., Kobler, J., Haas, E., Kiese, R., Kitzler, B. 2017. Historic nitrogen deposition determines future climate change effects on nitrogen retention in temperate forests. Climatic Change 144(2): 221-235
NS/NP		05/04/2018	Newsletter 8	Pisa, Italy	Abel Ramoelo, Moses A. Cho - CSIR	"Understanding seasonal variations of vegetation greening and senescence in the Southern African savannas", from the article: Response of Land Surface

Event Type	P /O	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
						Phenology to Variation in Tree Cover during Green-Up and Senescence Periods in the Semi-Arid Savanna of Southern Africa
NS/NP		08/01/2018	Release of the Booklet "SPACED: Using Earth Observation to Protect Natural Landscapes"	Barcelona and Pisa	Cristina Domingo, Joan Maso, Silvia Giamberini, Antonello Provenzale, B. Alfthan, T. Schoolmeister, M. Jurek, M. Andresen	SPACED: Using Earth Observation to Protect Natural Landscapes

TABLE 9-B: Organisation of events and workshops

DATE	kind of event (scientific topic/general)	Kind of EVENT	PLACE	Organiser	EVENT Title
05/04/2018	SP	Workshop on Cultural Ecosystem Services	Gerês, Portugal	Emilie Crouzat, Volker Grescho (UFZ/iDiv), Cláudia Carvalho-Santos (ICETA)	Workshop on Cultural Ecosystem Services in and around Peneda-Geres National Park
27/03/2018	SP	Workshop on Cultural Ecosystem Services	Molln, Austria	Emilie Crouzat, Volker Grescho, Aletta Bonn (UFZ/iDiv)	Workshop on Cultural Ecosystem Services in and around Peneda-Geres National Park
16/03/2018	SP	Workshop on Cultural Ecosystem Services	Zernez, Switzerland	Crouzat E., Grescho V., Bonn A. , Stritih A.	Workshop on Cultural Ecosystem Services in and around Peneda-Geres National Park
21.11.2017	SP	Citizen science Workshop	Roma, Italy	Emilie Crouzat (UFZ/iDiv)	Designing a guide about Citizen Science for environmental management in protected areas

DATE	kind of event (scientific topic/general)	Kind of EVENT	PLACE	Organiser	EVENT Title
25/10/2017	EW	WORKSHOP on Earth Observation for Ecosystem Services & Protected Areas Survey, ECOPOTENTIAL WP9 - Third Session PAs survey	Parco dei Castelli Romani, Rocca di Papa (RM), Italy	ISPRA: Valentini, E., Filippini, F., Nguyen Xuan, A., et al.	Mainstreaming EO products and services user-driven., 25h -26 Ottobre 2017
23-27/10/2017	SP	GEO Plenary meeting 2017	Washington DC, USA	Matthias Jurek / Silvia Giamberini / Antonello Provenzale	Earth Observation for achieving and monitoring mountain-related SDGs:
15-19/10/2017	SP	LTER-NEON-ECOPOTENTIAL projects joint meeting	Kibbutz Tzuba, Israel	Shayli Dor-Haim, Moshe Shachak ; Ehud Meron et al.	Workshop: Toward a unified framework for life supporting systems in the Anthropocene
12-14/09/2017	EW	Presentation of ECOPOTENTIAL Project	Ohrid, Resen	Orhideja Tasevska (HIO), Herman Hummel (NIOZ)	Workshop: "Requirements of Protected Areas - the role of environmental, cultural and socio-economic factors - a survey of EcoPotential WP9"
19-21/06/2017	SP	European GEO Workshop – EGW 2017	Helsinki, Finland	Antonello Provenzale - CNR	Organization of the Session: Global change impacts in mountain regions
19-21/06/2018	SP	European GEO Workshop – EGW 2017	Helsinki, Finland	Florian Wetzel (MfN)	Organization of the Session: How Ecosystem and Biodiversity data and knowledge can support the GEO objectives

DATE	kind of event (scientific topic/general)	Kind of EVENT	PLACE	Organiser	EVENT Title
16-19/01/2017	EW	ECOPOTENTIAL-SWOS joint meeting	Arles, France	Tour du Valat Geijzendorffer, Ilse, Poulin, B., Lefebvre, G., et al.	organisation of a joint project meeting SWOS and ECOPOTENTIAL
02-05/05/2017	EW	Workshop “Application of Earth Observation tools in protected areas”	Pisa, Italy	Silvia Giamberini / Assunta Donato/ Serena Botteghi / Federica Caiozzi - CNR	Workshop “Application of Earth Observation tools in protected areas”
19-23/02/2018	EW	Training Course and Workshop on the use of Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems	Pisa, Italy	Silvia Giamberini / Serena Botteghi / Stefania Lombardi / Federica Caiozzi - CNR	ECOPOTENTIAL Training Course on Remote Sensing and Modelling Applied to Natural Ecosystems

TABLE 9-C: Social media and website management

Event Type	DATE	EVENT kind	PLACE	Organiser	TITLE of EVENT
WEB	All reporting period	Management of ECOPOTENTIAL and Newsletter website	Pisa and Bari, Italy	Giulia Crema EBD-CSIC	Post on Facebook EBD-CSIC publication Front Ecol Environ doi:10.1002/fee.1459
SM	All reporting period	Management of Social Media Communication on Facebook and Twitter	Online	Asja Bernd and Yrneh Ulloa - UBT	Communication of project events, results and other aspects on Facebook and Twitter

WEB	01/12/2017	First release of the ECO POTENTIAL4SCHOOLS game platform	Lecce, Italy	Francesco Cozzoli - UNISALENTO	ECO POTENTIAL4SCHOOLS
WEB	20/07/2017	Ecopotential from Space website	Barcellona, Spain	Joan Maso - CREAM	ECO POTENTIAL from Space web browser
WEB	27/02/2018	Website-storymap about Pelagos Sanctuary	Arendal, Norway	Bjorn Alfthan - Tina Schoolmeister - Grid Arendal	Protecting Marine Mammals in Crowded Water https://grid-arendal.maps.arcgis.com/apps/Cascade/index.html?appid=54b862ef079445d9a99b8f6249249e4d

TABLE 9-D: Exhibitions

DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
08-12/01/2018	SPACED Photo Exhibition at the EU Parliament	Brussels, Belgium	ECOPOTENTIAL CONSORTIUM	SPACED: Using Earth Observation to Protect Natural Landscapes
01-28/01/2018	SPACED Photo Exhibition at the EU Committee of Regions	Brussels, Belgium	ECOPOTENTIAL CONSORTIUM / UNEP	SPACED: Using Earth Observation to Protect Natural Landscapes
23-27/10/2017	GEO Plenary meeting 2017	Washington DC, USA	Mariasilvia Giamberini, Assunta Donato CNR	ECOPOTENTIAL posters and videos @ the EUROGEOSS Stand
10/06/2017	"Campus Night" / 1. Osnabrücker Campus Nacht	Osnabrück, Germany	Danijela Markovic-Bredthauer; Oskar Kärcher et al.	Art and Science / Wissenschaft oder Kunst?
05-07/04/2017	Climateurope Festival 2017	Valencia, Spain	Ioannis Manakos - CERTH	ECOPOTENTIAL: Remote sensing for ecosystems
28/05/2018-30/06/2018	SPACED Photo Exhibition at the EU Parliament	Brussels, Belgium	ECOPOTENTIAL CONSORTIUM / UNEP	SPACED: Using Earth Observation to Protect Natural Landscapes

TABLE 9-E: Other dissemination events

Event Type	DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	PRESENTER	TITLE of PRESENTATION
O	15/05/2018	Scientific Colloquium	Zürich, Switzerland	Maik Billing (University of Potsdam)	Ecological sorting, plant competition and trait diversity: understanding forest dynamics with LPJmL-FIT
PE	20/03/2018	CPH:DOX Science Film Forum Research Projects 2018	Copenhagen, Denmark	Mariasilvia Giamberini and Asja Bernd - CNR - UBT	SPACED: protecting nature through Earth observation
O	18/1/2018	Dissemination of ECOPOTENTIAL results & achievements to the Greek Ministry of Rural Development and Food	Athens, Greece	Ioannis Manakos - CERTH	Presentation of ECOPOTENTIAL results/ achievements & the EODESM classification system
E	08-12/01/2018	SPACED Photo Exhibition at the EU Parliament	Brussels, Belgium	ECOPOTENTIAL CONSORTIUM	SPACED: Using Earth Observation to Protect Natural Landscapes
E	01-28/01/2018	SPACED Photo Exhibition at the EU Committee of Regions	Brussels, Belgium	ECOPOTENTIAL CONSORTIUM / UNEP	SPACED: Using Earth Observation to Protect Natural Landscapes
OE	26/10/2017	Survey, ECOPOTENTIAL - Third Session PAs survey	Parco dei Castelli Romani, Rocca di Papa (RM), Italy	ISPRA: Valentini, E., Filipponi, F., Chiesura, A.,	Supporting PAs manager for survey
OE	26/10/2017	Survey, ECOPOTENTIAL- Third Session PAs survey	Parco dell'Appia Antica(RM). Italy	ISPRA: Nguyen Xuan, A., Mirabile, M., Raudner, A.	Supporting PAs manager for survey
E	23-27/10/2017	GEO Plenary meeting 2017	Washington DC, USA	Mariasilvia Giamberini, Assunta Donato CNR	2 ECOPOTENTIAL posters @ the EUROGEOSS Stand
O	28/09/2017	Course on wetlands for Master students of an environmental management study	Arles, France	Geijzendorffer, Ilse (TdV)	Teaching Master students on the use of mapping methods of ecosystem services in the Camargue
O	28/09/2017	Course on wetlands for Master students of an	Arles, France	Geijzendorffer, Ilse (TdV)	Presentation of the Camargue

		environmental management study			
OE	08-12/09/2017	Summer School EEOBBS	Blagoevgrad, Bulgaria	Ioannis Manakos - CERTH	Application of Earth Observation in ecosystem services
OE	08-12/09/2017	Summer School EEOBBS	Blagoevgrad, Bulgaria	Ioannis Manakos - CERTH	Land-Cover Evolution Class in Image Time Series of Landsat and Sentinel-2 Based on Latent Dirichlet Allocation
E	10/06/2017	"Campus Night" / 1. Osnabrücker Campus Nacht	Osnabrück, Germany	Danijela Markovic-Bredthauer; Oskar Kärcher et al.	Art and Science / Wissenschaft oder Kunst?
OE	04-09/06/2017	Split Summer School	Dubrovnik, Croatia	Claudia Notarnicola (Eurac)	Biophysical parameters from remotely sensed imagery as a tool for monitoring and evaluating ecosystem biodiversity
O	07/04/2017	Meeting in French Institute	Skopje, Macedonia	Orhideja Tasevska - HIO	Presentation of ECOPOTENTIAL Project
E	05-07/04/2017	Climateurope Festival 2017	Valencia, Spain	Ioannis Manakos - CERTH	ECOPOTENTIAL: Remote sensing for ecosystems
O	27/03/2017	Presentation at EURAC	Bolzano, Italy	Antonello Provenzale - CNR	ECOPOTENTIAL: Improving future ecosystem benefits through Earth Observations
OE	29/09/2017	Researchers' night	Pisa, Italy	W / JA	O
OE	29/09/2017	Researchers' night	Thessaloniki, Greece	W / JA	O
OE	29/09/2017	Researchers' night	Heraklion, Greece	W / JA	O
OE	29/09/2017	Researchers' night	Granada, Spain	UniGranada Researchers	ECOPOTENTIAL H2020 project
E	28/05/2018-30/06/2018	SPACED Photo Exhibition at the EU Parliament	Brussels, Belgium	ECOPOTENTIAL CONSORTIUM / UNEP	SPACED: Using Earth Observation to Protect Natural Landscapes

Flyers

DATE	EVENT Title	PLACE	Authors	TITLE of Flyer
20/07/2017	Leaflet translation in Spanish	Spain	Spanish partners	Mejorando los beneficios futuros de los ecosistemas a través de la observación de la Tierra
20/07/2017	Leaflet translation in French	France	French partners	Observer la Terre pour protéger les écosystèmes et mieux bénéficier de leurs services dans le futur
20/07/2017	Leaflet translation in German	Germany/Austria	German/Austrian partners	Verbesserung zukünftiger Ökosystemleistungen mit Hilfe von Erdbeobachtung
01/07/2017	Leaflet translation in Italian	Italy/Switzerland	Italian / Swiss partners	Utilizzare le osservazioni della Terra per proteggere gli ecosistemi
20/12/2017	ECOPOTENTIAL Calendar 2018-2019	Pisa, Italy	Silvia Giamberini / Stefania Lombardi	ECOPOTENTIAL Calendar 2018-2019

11. Appendix 3 – List of scientific publications

In the following table, the list of ECOPOTENTIAL publications on peer reviewed journals is reported from the most recent to the oldest; Until publication n. 47 (included) it refers to the last reporting period (1 December 2016- 31 May 2018). Green and gold open access papers are distinguished. In the column “ECOP partner” the first author’s institution is reported in bold.

#	TITLE	AUTHORS	JOURNAL	Publication date	DOI	Open Access/ GD=gold; GN= green	ECOP partner
1	Uniqueness of Protected Areas for Conservation Strategies in the European Union	Hoffmann S., Beierkuhnlein C., Field R., Provenzale A., Chiarucci A.	Scientific Reports	24 April 2018	doi:10.1038/s41598-018-24390-3	GD	UBT, CNR
2	Modeling Soil Water Dynamics and Pasture Growth in the Montado Ecosystem Using MOHID Land	Simionesei L., Ramos T. B., Oliveira A. R., Jongen M., Darouich H., Weber K., Proença V., Domingos T., Neves R.	Water	16 April 2018	https://doi.org/10.3390/w10040489	GD	IST, MARETEC
3	Essential ocean variables for global sustained observations of biodiversity and ecosystem changes	Miloslavich P., Bax N. J., Simmons S. E., Klein E., Appeltans W., Aburto-Oropeza O., Andersen Garcia M., Batten S. D., Benedetti-Cecchi L., Checkley Jr. D. M., Chiba S., Duffy J. E., Dunn D. C., Fischer A., Gunn J., Kudela R., Marsac F., Muller-Karger F. E., Obura D., Shin Y.	Global Change Biology	10 April 2018	https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14108	GD	MARBEC, UNESCO

#	TITLE	AUTHORS	JOURNAL	Publication date	DOI	Open Access/ GD=gold; GN= green	ECOP partner
4	Detection of windthrows and insect outbreaks by L-band SAR: A case study in the Bavarian Forest National Park	Tanasea M. A., Aponte C., Mermozc S., Bouvetc A., Le Toanc T., Heurichde M.	Remote Sensing of Environment	19 March 2018	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2018.03.009	GD	UNSW
5	Monitoring biodiversity change through effective global coordination	Navarro L. M., Fernandez N., Guerra C., Guralnick R., Kissling W. D., Londono M. C., Muller-Karger F., Turak E., Balvanera P., Costello M. J., Delavaud A., El Serafy G., Ferrier S., Geijzendorffer I., Geller G. N., Jetz W., Kim E., Kim H., Martin C. S., McGeoch M. A., Mwampamba T. H., Nel J. L., Nicholson E., Pettorelli N., Schaepman M. E., Skidmore A., Pinto I. S., Vergara S., Vihervaara P., Xu H., Yahara T., Gill M. and Pereira H. M.	Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability	19 March 2018	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2018.02.005	GD	iDiv, UNEP-WCMC, TdV, Deltares

#	TITLE	AUTHORS	JOURNAL	Publication date	DOI	Open Access/ GD=gold; GN= green	ECOP partner
6	Satellite sensor requirements for monitoring essential biodiversity variables of coastal ecosystems	Muller-Karger F. E., Hestir E., Ade C., Turpie K., Roberts D. A., Siegel D., Miller R. J., Humm D., Izenberg N., Keller M., Morgan F., Frouin R., Dekker A. G., Gardner R., Goodman J., Schaeffer B., Franz B. A., Pahlevan N., Mannino A. G., Concha J. A., Ackleson S. G., Cavanaugh K. C., Romanou A., Tzortziou M., Boss E. S., Pavlick R., Anthony Freeman A., Rousseaux C. S., Dunne J., Long M. C., Klein E., McKinley G. A., Goes J., Letelier R., Kavanaugh M., Roffer M., Bracher A., Arrigo K. R., Dierssen H., Zhang X., Davis F. W., Best B., Guralnick R., Moisan J., Sosik H. M., Kudela R., Mouw C. B., Barnard A. H., Palacios S., Roesler C., Drakou E. G., Appeltans W., Jetz W.	Ecological application	6 March 2018	https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.1682	GD	UNESCO

#	TITLE	AUTHORS	JOURNAL	Publication date	DOI	Open Access/ GD=gold; GN= green	ECOP partner
7	Complementarity of the multidimensional functional and the taxonomic approaches to study phytoplankton communities in three Mediterranean coastal lagoons of different trophic status	Leruste A., Villéger S., Malet N., De Wit R., Bec B.	Hydrobiologia	06 March 2018	https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-018-3565-4	GD	CNRS
8	Environmental and anthropogenic factors affecting the increasing occurrence of shark-human interactions around a fast-developing Indian Ocean island	Lagabrielle E., Allibert A., Kiszka J.J., Loiseau N., Kilfoil J. P., Lemahieu A.	Scientific Reports	27 February 2018	doi:10.1038/s41598-018-21553-0	GD	Université de La Réunion, UM
9	Mapping Mediterranean Wetlands With Remote Sensing: A Good-Looking Map Is Not Always a Good Map	Perennou C., Guelmami A., Paganini M., Philipson P., Poulin B., Strauch A., Tottrup C., Truckenbrodt J., Geijzendorffer I. R.	Advances in Ecological Research	14 February 2018	https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.aecr.2017.12.002	GN	TdV
10	How will climate change affect endangered Mediterranean waterbirds?	Ramirez F., Rodriguez C., Seoane J., Figuerola J., Bustamante J.	PlosOne	13 February 2018	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0192702	GD	CSIC
11	Explaining Leaf Nitrogen Distribution in a Semi-Arid Environment Predicted on Sentinel-2 Imagery Using a Field Spectroscopy Derived Model	Ramoelo A., Cho M. A.	Remote Sensing	9 February 2018	https://doi.org/10.3390/rs10020269	GD	CSIR

#	TITLE	AUTHORS	JOURNAL	Publication date	DOI	Open Access/ GD=gold; GN= green	ECOP partner
12	The effect of microbial activity on soil water diffusivity	B. U. Choudhury, S. Ferraris, R. W. Ashton, D. S. Powlson, W. R. Whalley	European Journal of Soil Science	30 January 2018	doi:10.1111/ejss.12535	GD	CNR
13	Are optical indices good proxies of seasonal changes in carbon fluxes and stress-related physiological status in a beech forest?	Nestola E., Scartazza A., Di Baccio D., Castagna A., Ranieri A., Cammarano M., Mazzenga F., Matteucci G., Calfapietra C.	Science of the Total Environment	15 January 2018	10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.08.167	GD	CNR
14	Assessment of climate change effects on mountain ecosystems through a cross-site analysis in the Alps and Apennines	Rogora M., Frate L., Carranza M.L., Freppaz M., Stanisci A., Bertani I., Bottarin R., Brambilla A., Canullo R., Carbognani M., Cerrato C, Chelli S., Cremonese E., Cutini M., Di Musciano M., Erschbamer B., Godone D., Iocchi M., Isabellon M., Magnani A., Mazzola L., U. di Cella M, Pauli H., Petey M., Petriccione B., Porro F., Psenner R., Rossetti G., Scotti	Science of the Total Environment	27 December 2017	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.12.155		CNR, EURAC

#	TITLE	AUTHORS	JOURNAL	Publication date	DOI	Open Access/ GD=gold; GN= green	ECOP partner
		A., Sommaruga R., Tappeiner U., Theurillat J.-P., Tomaselli M., Viglietti D., Viterbi R, Vittoz P., Winkler M., Matteucci G.					
15	Radiometric Correction of Simultaneously Acquired Landsat-7/Landsat-8 and Sentinel-2A Imagery Using Pseudoinvariant Areas (PIA): Contributing to the Landsat Time Series Legacy	Padró, J.-C., Pons, X., Aragonés, D., Díaz-Delgado, R., García, D., Bustamante, J., ... Lange, M.	Remote Sensing	15 December 2017	doi:10.3390/rs9121319	GD	CREAF, CSIC, UFZ
16	Factors affecting forest dynamics in the Iberian Peninsula from 1987 to 2012. The role of topography and drought.	Vidal-Macua J. J., Ninyerola M., Zabala A., Domingo-Marimon C., Pons X.	Forest Ecology and Management	15 December 2017	doi:10.1016/j.foreco.2017.10.011.	GD	UAB
17	How can global conventions for biodiversity and ecosystem services guide local conservation actions?	Geijzendorffer I. R., van Teeffelen A. JA, Allison H., Braun D., Horgan K., Iturrate-Garcia M., João Santos M., Pellissier L., Prieur-Richard A., Quatrini S., Sakai S., Zuppinger-Dingley D.	Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability	11 December 2017	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2017.12.011	GN	TdV, UNEP-WCMC, ETH

#	TITLE	AUTHORS	JOURNAL	Publication date	DOI	Open Access/ GD=gold; GN= green	ECOP partner
18	A view-based model of data-cube to support big earth data systems interoperability	Nativi S., Mazzetti P., Craglia M.	Big Earth Data	4 December 2017	https://doi.org/10.1080/20964471.2017.1404232	GD	CNR
19	Ecosystem services in European protected areas: Ambiguity in the views of scientists and managers?	Hummel C., Provenzale A., Van Deer Meer J., Wijnhoven S., Nolte A., Poursanidis D., Janss G., Jurek M., Andresen M., Poulin B., Kobler J., Beierkuhnlein C., Honrado J., Razinkovas A., Stritih A., Bargmann T., Ziemba A., Bonet-Garcia F., Adamescu M., Janssen G., Hummel H.	PLoSOne	15 November 2017	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0187143	GD	NIOZ, CNR, Iceta, Deltares, CSIC, UNEP, TdV, EAA, UTB, InBIO/CIBIO, KU, ETH, UIB, UGR, UB
20	Linear Multi-Task Learning for Predicting Soil Properties Using Field Spectroscopy.	Qi H., Paz-Kagan T., Karnieli A. and Li S.	Remote Sensing	30 October 2017	doi:10.3390/rs9111099.	GD	BGU
21	River networks as ecological corridors: A coherent ecohydrological perspective	Rinaldo A., Gatto M., Rodriguez-Iturbe I.	Advances in Water Resources	14 October 2017	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advwatres.2017.10.005	GD	EPFL, POLIMI

#	TITLE	AUTHORS	JOURNAL	Publication date	DOI	Open Access/ GD=gold; GN= green	ECOP partner
22	Citizen science for assessing ecosystem services: Status, challenges and opportunities.	Schröter M., Kraemer R., Mantel M., Kabisch N., Hecker S., Richter A., Neumeier V. & Bonn A.	Ecosystem Services	12 October 2017	doi:10.1016/j.ecoser.2017.09.017.	GD	UFZ
23	Potential and realized connectivity of the seagrass <i>Posidonia oceanica</i> and their implication for conservation.	Jahnke M., Casagrandi R., Melià P., Schiavina M., Schultz S. T., Zane L., Procaccini G.	Diversity and Distributions	18 September 2017	https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12633	GN	POLIMI
24	Local-and Plot-Scale Measurements of Soil Moisture: Time and Spatially Resolved Field Techniques in Plain, Hill and Mountain Sites.	Raffelli G., Previati M., Canone D., Gisolo D., Bevilacqua I., Capello G., Biddoccu M., Cavallo E., Deiana R., Cassiani G., Ferraris S.	Water	15 September 2017	doi:10.3390/w9090706	GD	CNR
25	Validating MODIS and Sentinel-2 NDVI Products at a Temperate Deciduous Forest Site Using Two Independent Ground-Based Sensors	Lange M., Dechant B., Rebmann C., Vohland M., Cuntz M., Doktor D.	Sensors	11 August 2017	doi: 10.3390/s17081855	GD	UFZ
26	An island view of endemic rarity—Environmental drivers and consequences for nature conservation.	Irl S.D.H., Schweiger A.H., Medina F.M., Fernández-Palacios J.M., Harter D.E.V., Jentsch A., Provenzale A., Steinbauer M.J., Beierkuhnlein C.	Diversity and Distributions	6 August 2017	doi: 10.1111/ddi.12605	GD	UBT, CSIC, CNR

#	TITLE	AUTHORS	JOURNAL	Publication date	DOI	Open Access/ GD=gold; GN= green	ECOP partner
27	Historic nitrogen deposition determines future climate change effects on nitrogen retention in temperate forests.	Dirnböck T., Foldal C., Djukic I., Kobler J., Haas E., Kiese R., Kitzler B.	Climatic Change	21 July 2017	doi:10.1007/s10584-017-2024-y	GD	EAA
28	Snow water equivalent in the Alps as seen by gridded data sets, CMIP5 and CORDEX climate models.	Terzago, S., von Hardenberg, J., Palazzi, E., and Provenzale, A.	The Cryosphere	10 July 2017	doi: 10.5194/tc-11-1625-2017.	GD	CNR
29	Implications of sensor design for coral reef detection: Upscaling ground hyperspectral imagery in spatial and spectral scales.	Caras T. , Hedleyb J., Karnieli A.	Geoinformation	9 July 2017	doi: 10.1016/j.jag.2017.07.009.	GD	BGU
30	Response of Land Surface Phenology to Variation in Tree Cover during Green-Up and Senescence Periods in the Semi-Arid Savanna of Southern Africa	Cho M. A., Ramoelo A. and Dziba L.	Remote Sensing	4 July 2017	doi:10.3390/rs9070689	GD	CSIR
31	Sea ice phenology and primary productivity pulses shape breeding success in Arctic seabirds	Ramirez F., Tarroux A., Hovinen J., Navarro J., Afàn I., Forero M. G., Descamps S.	Scientific Reports	3 July 2017	10.1038/s41598-017-04775-6	GD	CSIC

#	TITLE	AUTHORS	JOURNAL	Publication date	DOI	Open Access/ GD=gold; GN= green	ECOP partner
32	Positive symplectic integrators for predator-prey dynamics	F. Diele, C. Marangi	Discrete and Continuous Dynamical Systems - Series B	July 2017	doi:10.3934/dcdsb.2017185	GD	CNR
33	r.pi: a GRASS GIS package for semi-automatic spatial pattern analysis of remotely sensed land cover data.	Wegmann M., Leutner B.F., Metz M., Neteler M., Dech S., Rocchini D	Methods in Ecology and Evolution	9 June 2017	doi: 10.1111/2041-210X.12827	GD	DLR, CNR (?)
34	Deep-Learning Convolutional Neural Networks for scattered shrub detection with Google Earth Imagery	Guirado, Emilio; Tabik, Siham; Alcaraz-Segura, Domingo; Cabello, Javier; Herrera, Francisco	Remote Sensing	3 June 2017	http://www.mdpi.com/2072-4292/9/12/1220	GD	CREAF
35	Comparing pixel and object based approaches to map an understory invasive shrub in tropical mixed forests.	Niphadkar M., Nagendra H., Tarantino C., Adamo M., & Blonda P.	Frontiers in Plant Science	31 May 2017	doi:10.3389/fpls.2017.00892	GD	CNR
36	Modeling Biomass Production in Seasonal Wetlands Using MODIS NDVI Land Surface Phenology.	Lumbierres M., Méndez P.F., Bustamante J., Soriguer R., Santamaría L.	Remote Sensing	21 April 2017	doi:10.3390/rs9040392	GD	CSIC

#	TITLE	AUTHORS	JOURNAL	Publication date	DOI	Open Access/ GD=gold; GN= green	ECOP partner
37	Priorities to Advance Monitoring of Ecosystem Services Using Earth Observation.	Cord A.F., Brauman K.A., Chaplin-Kramer R., Huth A., Ziv G., Seppelt R.	Trends in Ecology & Evolution	12 April 2017	doi:10.1016/j.tree.2017.03.003	GN	UFZ, UnivLeeds
38	On the key role of droughts in the dynamics of summer fires in Mediterranean Europe.	Turco M., von Hardenberg J., AghaKouchak A., Llasat M.C., Provenzale A., Trigo R.M.	Scientific reports	6 March 2017	doi:10.1038/s41598-017-00116-9	GD	CNR
39	A generalized definition of reactivity for ecological systems and the problem of transient species dynamics	Mari L., Casagrandi R., Rinaldo A., Gatto M.	Methods in Ecology and Evolution.	4 March 2017	doi: 10.1111/2041-210X.12805	GN	POLIMI, EPFL
40	Climate impacts on global hot spots of marine biodiversity.	Ramírez F., Afán I., Davis L.S., Chiaradia A.	Science Advances	22 February 2017	doi:10.1126/sciadv.1601198	GD	CSIC
41	Multi-modal knowledge base generation from very high-resolution satellite imagery for habitat mapping.	Manakos I., Technitou E., Petrou Z., Karydas C., Tomaselli V., Veronica G., Mountrakis G.	European Journal of Remote Sensing	17 February 2017	doi:10.5721/EuJRS20164953	GD	CERTH
42	Vulnerability of European freshwater catchments to climate change.	Markovic D., Carrizo S.F., Kärcher O., Walz A., David J.N.	Global Change Biology	10 February 2017	doi:10.1111/gcb.13657	GD	UP

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43	Creating a safe operating space for wetlands in a changing climate.	Green A.J., Alcorlo P., Peeters E.T.H.M., Morris E.P., Espinar J.L., Bravo M.A., Bustamante J., Díaz-Delgado R., Koelmans A.A., Mateo R., Mooij W.M., Rodríguez-Rodríguez M., van Nes E.H., Scheffer M.	Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment	9 February 2017	doi:10.1002/fee.1459	GN	CSIC
44	Validation of PROBA-V GEOV1 and MODIS C5 & C6 fAPAR Products in a Deciduous Beech Forest Site in Italy	Nestola E., Sánchez-Zapero J., Latorre C., Mazzenga F., Matteucci G., Calfapietra C., Camacho F.	Remote Sensing	4 February 2017	10.3390/rs9020126	GD	CNR
45	Estimating Invasion Success by Non-Native Trees in a National Park Combining WorldView-2 Very High Resolution Satellite Data and Species Distribution Models.	Monteiro A.T., Gonçalves J., Fernandes R.F., Alves S., Marcos B., Lucas R., Teodoro A.C., Honrado J.P.	Diversity	18 January 2017	doi:10.3390/d9010006	GD	CIBIO-InBIO, UNSW
46	Plant invasion and speciation along elevational gradients on the oceanic island La Palma, Canary Islands.	Steinbauer M. J., Irl S.D., González-Mancebo J.M., Breiner F.T., Hernández-Hernández R., Hopfenmüller S., Kidane Y., Jentsch A., Beierkuhnlein C.	Ecology and Evolution	27 December 2015	doi:10.1002/ece3.2640	GD	UBT

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47	Hyperspectral Sensors as a Management Tool to Prevent the Invasion of the Exotic Cordgrass <i>Spartina densiflora</i> in the Doñana Wetlands.	Bustamante J., Aragonés D., Afán I., Luque C.J., Pérez-Vázquez A., Castellanos E.M., Díaz-Delgado R.	Remote Sensing	8 December 2016	doi: 10.3390/rs8121001	GD	CSIC
48	Effect of Protection Level in the Hydroperiod of Water Bodies on Doñana's Aeolian Sands.	Bustamante J., Aragonés D., Afán I.	Remote Sensing	20 October 2016	doi: 10.3390/rs8100867	GD	CSIC
49	Towards Operational Detection of Forest Ecosystem Changes in Protected Areas.	Tarantino C., Lovergine F., Niphadkar M., Lucas R., Nativi S., Blonda P.	Remote Sensing	16 October 2016	https://doi.org/10.3390/rs8100850	GD	CNR, UNSW
50	Long-Term Monitoring of the Flooding Regime and Hydroperiod of Doñana Marshes with Landsat Time Series (1974–2014)	Díaz-Delgado R., Aragonés D., Afán I., Bustamante J.	Remote Sensing	20 September 2016	https://doi.org/10.3390/rs8090775	GD	CSIC
51	A comprehensive open package format for preservation and distribution of geospatial data and metadata.	Pons X., Masó J.	Computers & Geosciences	17 September 2016	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cageo.2016.09.001	GD	CREAF

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52	Definition and application of expert knowledge on vegetation pattern, phenology, and seasonality for habitat mapping, as exemplified in a Mediterranean coastal site.	Tomaselli V., Adamo M., Veronico G., Sciandrello S., Tarantino C., Dimopoulos P., Medagli P., Nagendra H., and Blonda P.	Plant Biosystems-An International Journal Dealing with all Aspects of Plant Biology	16 September 2016	10.1080/11263504.2016.1231143	GN	CNR, UNILE
53	National Ecosystem Assessments in Europe: A Review	Schroter M., Albert C., Marques A., Tobon W., Lavorel S., Maes J., Brown C., Klotz S., Bonn A.	BioScience	17 August 2016	https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biw101	GD	UFZ
54	Developing spatially and thematically detailed backdated maps for land cover studies.	Vidal-Macua J.J., Zabala A., Ninyerola M., Pons X.	International Journal of Digital Earth	4 August 2016	doi: 10.1080/17538947.2016.1213320	GD	CREAF
55	On the dynamics of a generalized predator–prey system with Z-type control.	Lacitignola D., Diele F., Marangi C., Provenzale A.	Mathematical Biosciences	27 July 2016	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mbs.2016.07.011	GD	CNR
56	Crowdsourcing: It Matters Who the Crowd Are. The Impacts of between Group Variations in Recording Land Cover.	Comber A., Mooney P., Purves R.S., Rocchini D., Walz A.	PlosOne	26 July 2016	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0158329	GD	UnivLeeds, CNR, UP

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57	Lake La Salada de Chiprana (NE Spain), an Example of an Athalassic Salt Lake in a Cultural Landscape.	De Wit R.	"Lake Sciences and Climate Change"	31 May 2016	http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/6443	GD	MARBEC
58	Earth Observation for Maritime Spatial Planning: Measuring, Observing and Modeling Marine Environment to Assess Potential Aquaculture Sites.	Valentini E., Filipponi F., Nguyen Xuan A., Passarelli F.M., Taramelli A.	Sustainability	28 May 2016	https://doi.org/10.3390/su8060519	GD	ISPRA
59	Decreasing Fires in Mediterranean Europe.	Turco M., Bedia J., Di Liberto F., Fiorucci P., von Hardenberg J., Koutsias N., Llasat M.-C., Xystrakis F., Provenzale A.	PlosOne	16 March 2016	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0150663	GD	CNR, CSIC
60	Geomorphic controls on elevational gradients of species richness.	Bertuzzo E., Carrara F., Mari L., Altermatt F., Rodriguez-Iturbe I., Rinaldo A.	Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences	16 February 2016	https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1518922113	GD	EPFL, POLIMI
61	Estimation of the Land Surface Albedo Changes in the Broader Mediterranean Area, Based on 12 Years of Satellite Observations.	Benas N., Chrysoulakis N.	Remote Sensing	2 December 2015	https://doi.org/10.3390/rs71215816	GN	FORTH

In the following table, the list of ECOPOTENTIAL publications other than papers on peer reviewed journals within the 2 reporting periods is reported; Until n. 17= second reporting period. Green and gold open access status is reported. In the partner column, the first author's partner is reported in bold

#	TITLE	AUTHORS	JOURNAL	Publication date	DOI	Open Access/ GD=gold; GN= green	ECOP partner
1	Changes in Alpine grassland of Grand Paradiso National Park (Italy): first results from CO ₂ fluxes monitoring programme	Baneschi I., Giamberini M.S., Viterbi R., Cerrato C., Imperio S., Ferraris S., Provenzale A.	6th Symposium for Research in Protected Areas - Conference Volume, 2- 3 November 2017, Faculty of Natural Sciences, University of Salzburg, Austria	27 March 2018	10.1553/np_symposium2017s1	GD	CNR
2	The management of wild reindeer (Rangifer tarandus) in Hardangervidda National Park, Norway	Bargmann T. & Vetaas O.R.	6th Symposium for Research in Protected Areas	27 March 2018	10.1553/np_symposium2017s1	GD	UIB
3	Threats of Climate Change to Single-Island Endemic Species in Protected Areas	Beierkuhnlein C. & Irl S.D.H.	6th Symposium for Research in Protected Areas	27 March 2018	10.1553/np_symposium2017s1	GD	UBT
4	Ecosystem services provided by the bio-physical structure of natural capital in the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve Romania	Cazaku C. & Adamescu M.C.	6th Symposium for Research in Protected Areas	27 March 2018	10.1553/np_symposium2017s1	GD	UB
5	From long-term ecosystem monitoring to regional modelling of ecosystem function in the National Park Kalkalpen, Austria	Dirnböck T., Kobler J., Kraus D., Schindlbacher A., Seidl R., Mirtl M.	6th Symposium for Research in Protected Areas	27 March 2018	10.1553/np_symposium2017s1	GD	EAA

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6	Endemic vascular plants in the high mountains of the Sierra Nevada National Park (Spain)	Eibes P.M., Kienle D., Beierkuhnlein C.	6th Symposium for Research in Protected Areas	27 March 2018	10.1553/np_symposium2017s1	GD	UBT
7	Evaluating the potential of protected areas to preserve biodiversity at large scales. A multi-taxa approach in mountain ecosystem: a shared protocol between 6 Italian Parks	Hoffmann S. & Beierkuhnlein C.	6th Symposium for Research in Protected Areas	27 March 2018	10.1553/np_symposium2017s1	GD	UBT
8	Ecosystem Services and Pressures in European Protected Areas: Divergent Views of Environmental Scientists and Managers	Hummel C., Boyer Y., Jurek M., Andresen P.M., Kobler J., Beierkuhnlein C., Provenzale A., Ziv G., Heurich M., Kordelas G., De Wit R., Manakos I., Hummel, H.	6th Symposium for Research in Protected Areas	27 March 2018	10.1553/np_symposium2017s1	GD	NIOZ, CNR, UBT, UNEP, CERTH, UnivLeeds, UM
9	Effects of protection status, climate, and water management of rice fields on long-term population dynamics of herons and egrets in north-western Italy	Imperio S., Ranghetti L., Von Hardenberg J., Provenzale A., Boncompagni E., Fasola M.	6th Symposium for Research in Protected Areas	27 March 2018	10.1553/np_symposium2017s1	GD	CNR
10	Remote sensing based comprehensive monitoring of land cover change in protected areas	Gedon L., Sonnenschein R., Walz A.	6th Symposium for Research in Protected Areas	27 March 2018	10.1553/np_symposium2017s1	GD	UP, EURAC
11	Survival in litte? Refugia of high-elevated plants in the Spanish Sierra Nevada	Kienle D., Eibes P.M., Beierkuhnlein C.	6th Symposium for Research in Protected Areas	27 March 2018	10.1553/np_symposium2017s1	GD	UBT

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12	CORINE for large-scale monitoring of PAs in Europe	Walz A. & Korup O.	6th Symposium for Research in Protected Areas	27 March 2018	10.1553/np_symposium2017s1	GD	UP
13	EcoPortal: a proposition for a semantic repository dedicated to ecology and biodiversity	Fiore N., Barbara Magagna B., Gold- farb D.	Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop on Semantics for Biodiversity, S4BioDiv'17	17 January 2018	https://hal-lirmm.ccsd.cnrs.fr/lirmm-01605671/	GD	UniSalento
14	Integrated land cover and change classifications. In: The Roles of Remote Sensing in Nature Conservation: A Practical Guide and Case Studies (Eds. Díaz-Delgado, Richard Lucas and Clive Hurford), pp. 295-308.	Lucas R., Mitchell A.	The Roles of Remote Sensing in Nature Conservation - A Practical Guide and Case Studies	2017	ISBN-13: 978-3319643304	?	UNSW
15	On the interest of the spectral bands in the automatic selection of high quality MODIS data through spatial pattern identification	Domingo-Marimon C., Pesquer L., Gomez-Cabajo N., Jimenez M., Pons X	Proceedings SPIE 10427, Image and Signal Processing for Remote Sensing XXIII (Warsaw, Poland, 2017)	4 October 2017	10.1117/12.2278596	GN	CREAF

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16	Remote sensing in the reflective spectrum: a powerful and applied technology for terrestrial ecosystem science.	Karnieli A.	Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Infrastructures: Challenges, New developments and Perspectives.	22 February 2017	<u>ISBN: 978-1-4987-5131-5</u>	GN	BGU
17	Comprehensive and Coordinated Approach of GEOSS to Ecosystem Challenges.	Provenzale A., Nativi S.	Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Infrastructures: Challenges, New developments and Perspectives.	22 February 2017	<u>ISBN: 978-1-4987-5131-5</u>	GN	CNR
18	Changes in tropical forest: assessing different detection techniques.	Tarantino C., Blonda P., Adamo M., Niphadkar M., Lucas. R.	A Sourcebook of Methods and Procedures for Monitoring Essential Biodiversity Variables in Tropical Forests with Remote Sensing	December 2016	<u>ISSN: 2542-6729.</u>	GD	CNR, UNSW